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METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and
Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D11.2

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation progress report

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Responsible Partner:	VILABS
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Editor(s):	Danai Kyrkou (ViLabs) Charalampos (Mpampis) Chatzimallis (ViLabs)
Contributor(s):	All Partners
Reviewer(s):	CYPOL, SIMAVI, and All Partners
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Abstract:	This report includes information on WP11 progress, partners' dissemination and communication activities, synergies with other projects, and the project exploitation plan. It also provides information on the regulatory and standardisation activities of the project.
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Executive Summary

This report is the second interim version of D11.1, “Dissemination, Communication and exploitation Plan and Material”. The first version was delivered during project month M6 (and was updated on M10), and the last one will be submitted to the European Commission by the end of the project – month 36.

The present deliverable describes the progress of the dissemination activities (online and offline) achieved during the project period M6-M18, including the project website, social media channels, newsletters, scientific publications, workshops, and third-party events. It also attempts to indicate any changes or improvements concerning the initial Dissemination Plan. In addition, information on the tools used to properly monitor and report the activities relevant to the current document is also provided. Finally, the present document report includes information about the initial METICOS Exploitation strategy and initial market analysis, as well as information on the regulatory and standardisation activities.

It needs to be noted that for the development and execution of the relevant Task, the WP Leader, as well as all the involved members, have advised and considered the following official EU document guidelines¹, in full line with the contractual agreement and corresponding articles.

¹ Commission, E., 2022. *Communicating Your Project - H2020 Online Manual*. [online] Ec.europa.eu. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm> [Accessed 28 January 2022]. and Commission, E., 2022. *Dissemination & Exploitation - Open Access - H2020 Online Manual*. [online] Ec.europa.eu. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm> [Accessed 28 January 2022].

1. Introduction

The current deliverable aims to present the progress and results of the METICOS dissemination and communication strategy for the period M6-M18 (February 2021 to February 2022). Also, an initial exploitation plan has been employed, promoting the exploitation and sustainability of the project and its' initial market analysis. In this regard, the present report includes the following:

- Updates on the dissemination and communication strategy
- Progress report on the communication channels and activities, both online and offline
- Progress report on the KPIs
- Initial exploitation strategy and business modelling of METICOS
- Initial Market analysis

The dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan is an active, ongoing process, regularly updated and assessed based on the forthcoming project's achievements and contributions from partners. The plan describes the individual partner responsibilities and timelines, guidelines, and suggestions for dissemination and communication under the continuous monitoring of the "WP11: Raising awareness and exploitation roadmap – METICOS standardisation activities" leader.

1.1 Intended audience

This document constitutes the progress report of dissemination communication and exploitation activities that are taking place during the period of interest, thus project months 6 to 18. It is a practical tool for the project's dissemination manager and all project partners to efficiently present but also evaluate their individual and collective dissemination and communication activities and secure the proper implementation of expected project activities and objectives. They can also identify the needs and re-adjust the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, following an agile process.

In addition, the document can be used as a guide and practical tool for "Horizon2020" – "Horizon Europe" dissemination managers of on-going and future projects, who will be willing to explore METICOS strategy and capitalise on it, as well as a dissemination guide/control point for the reviewers of the European Commission.

Last, the current deliverable report can be used by any possible future replicator of the METICOS dissemination approach.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is structured into the following ten sections: Chapter 1, "Introduction", introduces the document's intended audience and its structure. Chapter 2, "Dissemination and Communication Strategy", describes the updates on the existing strategy. Chapter 3 provides information on the "Reporting of Dissemination Activities & Statistics" to demonstrate the strategy's effectiveness. Chapter 4 presents the Synergies with other Projects and Initiatives, while Chapter 5 presents the "Monitoring and Evaluation" of the KPIs. It is followed by Chapter 6, "Exploitation Strategy and Business Models" of METICOS. Chapter 7 provides the "METICOS initial Market analysis". Chapter 8 consists of the "Regulatory and standardisation reporting". Chapter 9 is the conclusions of this deliverable report. Two Annexes containing the reporting templates are also available in Chapter 10.

2. Dissemination and Communication Strategy Updates

The concrete dissemination and communication strategy has been defined in detail in Project Deliverable 11.1 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material” which is available, under the section “[Public Deliverables](#)” in the project website as well as on METICOS [Zenodo Community](#). The five “W”s strategy, used, provides a clear step by step guide on its proper implementation and attaining the maximum impact for the project. This includes engagement of the stakeholders, awareness building, feedback extraction, and collaboration fostering. Furthermore, the strategy foresees actions during the whole duration of the project, both internally and externally, to achieve the best possible outreach of METICOS. The communication and dissemination strategy followed during the period of interest was in complete alliance with the needs and objectives identified in D11.1 and is, of course, adapted to the emerging needs and incidents.

For the period of interest, there are four worth mentioning updates of that strategy:

- **METICOS communication and dissemination policy** updated in line with the comments received during the last project Technical Review. Following the recommendations received on project month ten and during the first technical review meeting, and in line with the ethical review meeting and its’ results, Communication and Dissemination leader, as well as all project partners, have proceeded to an update of the understanding and planning of communication and dissemination strategy of METICOS project. All upcoming project communication and dissemination activities will reassure that system's weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities, will be appropriately indicated. The inclusion of these “indications” will be of great significance. It will give space to the “market” to also receive information about the limitations and weaknesses of METICOS, its’ approach or technological components, and its’ **benefits**. This will also provide the floor for additional knowledge creation, needs identification and solution development to satisfy the identified limitations and needs, providing the ground and possibility for further exploitation.
- **METICOS Communication/Dissemination upscaling via the Website re-structure**: The updates include new and updated sections and pages, in order to transform the METICOS project website into a portal of information for relevant researchers as well as Border Authorities and relevant stakeholders.
- WP11 is about to start shifting the communication and dissemination activities’ orientation towards **the Key Exploitable results and the upcoming exploitation** potentials.
- **METICOS social media strategy and engagement**: Updates relevant to the accessibility of user/visitor in terms of communication with project representatives, engagement with channels and content, as well as the sense of community belonging.

2.1 Updates on Dissemination Tools and Channels

The current section provides information on the updates on METICOS dissemination tools and channels, based on the initial strategy and planning defined in detail in METICOS project deliverable report D11.1.

2.1.1 METICOS Website re-structure

The project’s website operates as the major source of the project’s identity, goals, and actions, from which every stakeholder category can be informed. In other words, the METICOS website is a central dissemination and communication tool of the project providing the main results of the METICOS research and outcomes. In this respect, the communication managers of the project are constantly working on the optimisation of the user’s experience as well as to provide means and ways to connect: all communication and dissemination tools, channels, repositories, material, documents, presentations, social media and such are linked to (provide easy ways to connect with) the project website.

As briefly mentioned above, there were a few changes during this reporting period:

Active user engagement: In order to facilitate an active and effective engagement with website users/visitors, the primary contact information, (project’s info email, the contact details of the Project Coordinator and Dissemination and Exploitation Leader, along with the social media accounts and the newsletter subscription), is being provided in different places in the project website, on the website footer – static at all sub-pages and website sections as well as on the menu tab “Contact” – easy to read and find by all website visitors.

Figure 1 METICOS Contact details

Research and News portal: Under, the page “Communication”, an updated tab has been included titled “Related events” that directs the user to a list of third parties’ events and conferences organised by international agencies, fora, and institutions around the domain that METICOS covers. This, along with the Blog posts, the scientific publications of the project as well as a listing of all relevant and available scientific papers around the area of interest, further transform the project website into a portal of knowledge for relevant researchers as well as border authorities and practitioners.

Figure 2 Related Events under Communication SubMenu

A new tab titled “Events” focused on the events that METICOS has participated in has also been included, providing accessible information to relevant stakeholders and website visitors.

Figure 3 METICOS new event section

Ending, updates have taken place also in the following website sub-menus and sections, in line with the feedback received during the first technical meeting: a) the “About” section has been updated in order to provide the users with the overall scope aims and goals of the project in an easy readable way as well as the objectives, a link to the CORDIS project card and an overview of the project consortium (partnership map as well as partners logo). It works as a bridge to the next section/sub-tab where detailed information is provided per project partner b) the “Consortium” page has been updated in order to provide partner information with a more easy to read structure, c) the “Platform” page has been updated providing information on METICOS expected technological solution, as it was described in the contractual agreement (it needs to be noted that additional and more detailed information will be provided in line with the actual process and progress of development), d) the “Pilot” page relevant to the application trials, has also been updated with information derived also from the contractual

agreement. Updated and more detailed information will be provided in the upcoming period in line with the expected actions on behalf of the project and the implementation strategy that the responsible WP leaders are developing.

Figure 4 Home page of the METICOS website: New “Contact” page and updated sub-menus of “Synergies” and “Communication”

Common Space for relevant projects: Under the page “Synergies”, one can access the sup-page “H2020 BES Cluster” that contains all the information about the cluster and its members as well as goals and intentions for upcoming activities. This shared space provides information about the H2020 BES Cluster, and it is updated frequently.

Blog section/News section: Updates in terms of content once information is available and according to the security/privacy and ethical standards set out by the project consortium and by the Ethics Management Board in particular. Following the project progress in terms of theory and technology development as well as in terms of pilot activities, the news post ratio will be raised, while it is expected by all project partners to provide short publishable blog entries.

Library of content - Scientific articles & publications: The proper and more effective identification of opportunities to contribute to scientific knowledge and international literature can occur via the METICOS consortium's participation in conferences and workshops. METICOS partners have developed an online list of upcoming conferences, listing them according to the area of focus, the date of the conference, the country of venue, fees, possibility to submit a publication, the corresponding partner that should participate and such other information. This list is being available under the project sub-page “Events”. For the period of interest METICOS project has successfully proceeded with the submission of a series of scientific publications, the details of which is available below in the relevant section and will also be available accompanied with the actual content for free on the project website as soon as they are accepted and published. In addition to those, METICOS will proceed with the identification of publications issued by project partners or members of the H2020 BES Cluster and share them as “interesting readings”, creating this way a library of content and information under the project website. The latter will take place in full line with the European Commission guidelines on [open access](#) and with the full acknowledgement as well as the agreement of the corresponding authors.

2.1.2 Social Media Strategy & Accounts

The Social Media strategy has been clearly defined from the very first relevant Deliverable: D11.1: “Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material” which provided the detailed strategy and plan to be followed until the very completion of the project activities, pointing out also the different stages that will be followed. Of course, the social media strategy is in line with the overall communication and dissemination strategy, as part of the latter, and is being updated/adjusted according to the needs, barriers and opportunities that come across throughout the project implementation period.

For the period of concern, METICOS Dissemination team has explored all new features of social media marketing strategies and tools, in order to reach the project KPIs successfully. METICOS continued its successful social media strategy, based on tailor-made messages according to the content and characters permitted by each platform, with posts to be accompanied by visual elements and useful links to the project website, along with the pre-defined hashtags, and the “mentioning” features, to activate and engage other cluster members and synergies, other third projects, institutional accounts and networks, transforming them to beacons of METICOS content and information.

The social media accounts of METICOS remain the same as described in detail under D11.1, as they have been active quite early along with the initiation of the project activities. In addition, there were five tools and features updates on the communication tools in this reporting period to optimise their impact.

A. In terms of branding and engagement: A new social media banner, tailored to each social media channel was created containing a) the full project title, as in the social media accounts the “user name”, is the project acronym, b) a new barcode icon leading directly to METICOS project website, making the journey from Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn to the project website much easier for the user as well as more interesting as it creates an anticipation on behalf of the user, c) an explicit mention to the European Commission – Funding Agency via the use of the EC flag along with the funding statement. The use of the funding statement has a dual purpose: first, to follow EC guidelines in terms of communication of the funding agency and, secondly, to build on the credibility of METICOS social media channels and thus support further engagement. The banners are presented in the following figures.

Figure 5 The new METICOS banner

B. Use of the “New Facebook page” feature: From the very first moment when the feature of the “new Facebook page” became available, METICOS updated its’ page accordingly. By selecting this, METICOS account (so far, a page directly linked and managed via the personal profiles of the administrators) activated a dedicated news feed related not to the “likes/follows” of the administrator’s personal profile but to the “likes” of METICOS Facebook page. This makes it much easier to discover and join relevant conversations, follow relevant trends and news as well as actively interact with relevant stakeholders and EU projects and initiatives. The transfer also supports easier navigation between the personal profiles of the administrators and the METICOS page, updated task-based admin controls, dedicated notifications as well as provision for safety and integrity by supporting the detection of spam content and fake accounts that could potentially interact with project social media in a harmful way. In terms of interaction and engagement, the METICOS Facebook page is now available to hold Q&A on its very page – a feature that will be used in upcoming public events that will be held online.

Figure 6 METICOS new Facebook page

C. Facebook: from METICOS Likes to METICOS followers: METICOS Facebook page focuses on the “Followers” rather than “Likes”, as “Follow” is the button that appears first to new

users/visitors. The “Follower” indicator is a much stronger indicator/ much better signal of the number of people who do want to receive METICOS information and posts in their feeds, as a “Like” is not necessary also a “Follow”.²

D. Engaged community: In order to provide the possibility to METICOS users to follow project progress and stay connected, all relevant Social Links of Twitter and LinkedIn have been included in the Facebook channel.

Figure 7 Facebook page info section

E. User engagement - The use of action buttons: A new action button, in addition to the one of “Like” or “Follow”, is now available to the user/visitor of METICOS Facebook page that leads to the subscription form of METICOS E-Newsletter, providing to user/visitor the opportunity to sign up in an easy and fast way to projects’ news and updates on user’s email accounts.

Figure 8 Facebook page action buttons

² Facebook.com. 2021. *About Likes and Follows for New Pages Experience*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.facebook.com/business/help/2683010948601738?id=418112142508425>> [Accessed 17 February 2022].

3. Reporting of Dissemination Activities & Statistics

This chapter maps the communication channels’ progress for the respective reporting period. It includes metrics from the website and the social media accounts, the external activities the consortium has participated in, the newsletters, and the promotion of METICOS through partners’ networks.

3.1 Project website performance

As mentioned above, the communication manager worked on updating and optimising the website. In this respect, the communication managers audit the website's performance to have a clear picture of its outreach. Google Analytics allows the mapping of the traffic and tracking of the numbers of visitors and other relevant metrics over the last year of the project.

In the figures below, the results from this reporting period, from M6 to M18, are presented:

User acquisition

Starting with the website performance, based on the Google Analytics tool, the first category we observe is the User acquisition, to obtain an overview of our users’ behaviour.

Figure 9 User acquisition

According to figure 9, we observe the following numbers: 1329 new users, 1530 Engaged sessions, 61% engagement rate, 1.13 engaged sessions per user, 1m24s average engagement time, and 17878 event counts. The communication manager assesses these numbers regularly and tracks the website's shortcomings to find the most efficient way for its optimisation.

An explanation of terms is available below:

- Users: A person browsing the website (technically, a unique browser cookie)

- New users: The number of users who interacted with your site or launched your app for the first time (event-triggered: first open).
- Sessions: A single visit to your website, consisting of one or more page views, along with events, e-commerce transactions, and other interactions
- Engaged sessions: The number of sessions that lasted longer than 10 seconds, had a conversion event or had two or more screen or page views.
- Engagement rate: The percentage of engaged sessions. (Engaged sessions divided by sessions).
- Engaged sessions per user: Engaged sessions divided per user
- Average engagement time: The average length of time that the app was in the foreground or the website had a focus in the browser.
- Event count: The number of times your users triggered an event.

Pages and screens

Another important piece of information about the website, refer to the most popular pages. By tracking them, the communication manager can understand what the visitors are more interested in and can organise a more efficient communication plan for each page.

Figure 10 Popular pages

According to the figure above, during months 6 to 18, we observe the following numbers: 6552 views with 4.85 views per user.

Additional definitions are presented below:

- Views: The number of app screens or web pages your users saw. Repeated views of a single screen or page are counted. ([screen view](#) + [page view](#) events).
- Views per user: Views divided per users

The most popular page is the home page (2344 views), followed by the pages “About” (529 views), “Consortium” (452 views), and “Related projects” (426 views). Next, we have the page “H2020 BES Cluster” (243 views). The users frequently visit the pages that provide information about the project and the partnership. Also, since the page “Related Projects” was converted into “H2020 BES Cluster” during this reporting period, it is valid to sum their views, which gives us a total of 669 views, making it the second most popular page on the METICOS website. This number shows that there is an interest in the synergies the METICOS project is forming. Considering this, the communication manager puts great effort into the constant expansion of the METICOS network, either by inviting other related projects to the BES Cluster or by organising communication activities with them.

3.2 Social media and online channels

Social Media channels enable the dissemination and communication activities, enhancing the project's outreach. This section aims to present some representative elements of the impact of METICOS social media and the results of this reporting period (M6-M18) per social media channels. The feature provided by the social media platforms has played an important role for the organisations and the communications of the project's events, also working as the key info point and a point of reference even at the project's website. Furthermore, social media is used for interacting with various target groups such as other EU funded projects working on Smart Borders, EU policymakers, and other interested parties working on this sector.

The URLs of METICOS's social media accounts can be found below:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/meticos.eu/>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/MeticosEU>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/meticos-eu/>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCYIDKOkLGnL0eMXM0nle3KA>
- Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/meticos_eu_project/

3.2.1 Facebook

[METICOS Facebook page](#) currently counts 520 followers. It is mainly used to publicise relevant news, the project's progress and activities, tools and material developed by the project, as well as events organised either by the project or by the project's collaborators, where the public could participate, be informed, and fully engaged. In terms of user reach, the METICOS Facebook account has reached 8.825 users. In addition, the METICOS Facebook page counts more than 330 reactions to the published content and more than 220 link clicks to additional content or information.

Figure 11 METICOS Facebook page

Figure 12 Facebook insights - new appearance

Figure 13 Audience breakdown

3.2.2 Twitter

The [METICOS account on Twitter](#), which currently has 206 followers, is mainly used to promote participatory activities, awareness-raising events, exploitation activities and the project progress in general. It is a great tool to connect with most of our relevant stakeholders. A screenshot below presents the Twitter profile with the logo on the profile image and a tailored cover page, which makes the profile friendlier and warmer for the users, creating a positive feeling. Users have access to a short description of the project as well as to the link leading to the project website.

Figure 14 METICOS twitter account

Since Twitter divides the reporting periods into trimesters, we added up the periods separately. The overall numbers for M6-M18 are presented in Table 1 below. The METICOS Twitter account has a total of 26.5K impressions, with an engagement rate of 5.8% per post:

Impressions	26.5K
Engagement	1537
Engagement rate	5.8%

Table 1 Twitter performance Feb'21-Feb'22

Indicatively, we present below the months May and June that had better performance with a total of 10.1K impressions and an average of 2.8% engagement rate per post (figure 15). During this period, the tweets were increased, creating more traffic. Also, the members of the consortium participated in various events organised from the cluster projects, as well as other stakeholders like the European Commission and FRONTEX.

Figure 15 May-June 2021 performance

In addition, METICOS has initiated the [BES EU Projects Twitter list](#). It is a public Twitter list that transforms the general Twitter timeline to a BES timeline, keeping the user up to date with the latest developments, news, events as well as opportunities to communicate their project.

Figure 16 BES Cluster Twitter list

3.2.3 LinkedIn

Figure 17 METICOS LinkedIn page

The [METICOS LinkedIn page](#) currently counts 398 followers from different industries, like Research (22.19%), Higher Education (12.88%), Information Technologies and Services (11.51%), and such. Also, METICOS followers come from different places around Europe, such as Belgium, Austria, the UK, Spain, Norway, France, the Netherlands, Romania, and Italy (figure 18). It is encouraging to see that the project has gained followers from many different industries and locations, which means that people from different backgrounds are interested in learning more about the Social Impact & Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technologies.

Figure 18 LinkedIn Analytics – Followers main industries and locations

The page gained more than **8572** impressions during this reporting period, with May, November, and December being the months with the best performance (figure 19). The engagement rate is up to 13.79%, with August being the month with the highest engagement (figure 20).

Figure 19 Post impressions

Figure 20 Engagement rate

3.3 METICOS Newsletter

3.3.1 Subscription

METICOS develops and disseminates approximately one newsletter per 6 months (and according to project available news and needs) with project news to inform the subscribers about past and upcoming activities and events. Currently, it counts 120 subscribers. The subscription option is available at the bottom of the METICOS website. No pop-up windows or advertising windows are added. By selecting subscribe, the user is transferred to a new dedicated (and provided by MailChimp) window to safely provide their contact information (simply their email addresses). The procedure ends with a humanity process confirmation. The appearance of the page has been updated and can be seen in figure 21:

Figure 21 METICOS newsletter subscription process

3.3.2 METICOS issues

In this reporting period, two newsletters have been created:

1. [Newsletter issue 2 \(13/03/2021\)](#):

This newsletter issue was an opportunity for the project to introduce itself to the subscribers and explain what METICOS is. Also, it presented the consortium and the upcoming and past events, as well as the synergies that later constituted the H2020bescluster. The topics of the newsletter are presented below:

- *What is METICOS?*
- *Project Consortium*
- *News and Events*
- *METICOS on FRONTEX list*
- *METICOS Synergies*
- *Synergy members*

Figure 22 METICOS newsletter – 2nd issue

2. [Newsletter issue 3 \(28/02/2022\)](#):

This newsletter issue presents interesting information about the progress of METICOS until project month 18. The topics included in the newsletter are the following:

- *Participation of METICOS in external events (past and upcoming ones)*
- *Submission of papers from consortium members and presentations to EU level conferences*
- *List of the upcoming related conferences*
- *New H2020 BES Cluster members*
- *New twitter features*
- *Media Kit Sup-page*
- *Project Consortium*

Figure 23 METICOS newsletter - 3rd issue

3.4 Promotion through partners' network

METICOS partners use their network and social media channels to facilitate the dissemination of the project and its activities. METICOS takes advantage of their already established community of followers who trust them. Partners reshare the communication material created by the communication manager or produce their own, helping the project achieve more prominent visibility. All project partners put an effort into communicating METICOS activities through their social media channels and official websites. Below some examples can be found:

3.4.1 Website

The partners' official websites are a channel that METICOS leverages to achieve better reach. The partners host a dedicated page on their official websites to inform the visitors that they are members of the METICOS consortium and present the project and its actions. Also, they use hyperlinks to direct the users to the METICOS website or the project's social media accounts. The partners share news about the project on their website, mainly regarding the METICOS participation in third-party events, like conferences and workshops. Some examples are presented below from CERIDES, VILABS, ICCS, and Gruppo Maggioli.

Figure 24 [METICOS presentation on CERIDES website](#)

Figure 25 [METICOS presentation on ViLabs website](#)

f in

ΕΠΙΣΕΥ
Νέα
Το ΕΠΙΣΕΥ
Προκηρύξεις
Ερευνητικά Έργα
Εργαστήρια ΕΠΙΣΕΥ
English

🕒 24/04/2021
👤 YianXan
📅 Horizon H2020

Proposal ID: 883075
 ICCS project ID: 63113700
 Role: Partner
 Acronym: METICOS
 Topic: SU-BES01-2018-2019-2020
 Type of action: RIA
 Call identifier: H2020-SU-SEC-2018-2019-2020

METICOS: A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Duration in months: 36
 Fixed keyword 1: Detection, identification and authentication

Figure 26 [METICOS presentation on NTUA websites \(ICCS\)](#)

METICOS
Big Data Analytics, Detection Technologies, Smart Border control, Smart Border management - A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Security

METICOS

Call: H2020-SU-SEC-2018-2019-2020
Topic: SU-BES01-2019: "Human factors, and social, societal, and organisational aspects of border and external security"
Type: RIA
References: Grant Agreement No. 883075
Duration: Set 2020 – Ago 2023 (36 months)
Budget: € 4.997.481,25
ReFunding: € 4.997.481,25
Role: System Integrator, Technological Provider
Website: <https://meticos-project.eu/>
LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/meticos-eu/>
Twitter: <https://twitter.com/MeticosEU>
Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/meticos.eu/>

Details and Information

METICOS project

METICOS aims to introduce Big Data Analysis of border control information systems, in order to provide a step-change towards more modern and efficient Smart Border management and towards gaining societal and political acceptance of modern control technologies of EU borders such as "no gate solutions". It is therefore positioned as an initiative to create a real-time decision-support system with regard to different Smart Border control technologies that empowers two major stakeholder groups within the European border control sector (i.e., travellers and border control authorities & service providers) to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency.

To this end, the METICOS project will develop a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and users acceptance of border control technologies like

Partners

- ▶ Europea University Cipro (Cyprus)
- ▶ Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (Greece)
- ▶ Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
- ▶ Austrian Institute of Technology (Austria)
- ▶ Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Belgium)
- ▶ Net-U Consultants Ltd. (Cyprus)
- ▶ Siveco Romania (Romania)
- ▶ **Maggioli S.p.A. (Italy)**
- ▶ ViLabs Ltd (Greece)
- ▶ Johanniter Österreich Ausbildung und Forschung (Austria)

Figure 27 [METICOS presentation on Maqqioli website](#)

Figure 28 [METICOS participating in FRONTEX event \(CERIDES\)](#)

Figure 29 [METICOS at the European association for biometrics and the research projects conference](#)

3.4.2 Social media

METICOS consortium promotes the project and its activities through their social media accounts as well. The posts mainly promote the participation of METICOS in third party events or support the communication activities of the project. Sample posts can be found below:

Figure 30 CERIDES Facebook post for METICOS participation in the EAB Conference

Figure 31 CERIDES Tweet about METICOS participation in the FRONTEX workshop

Figure 32 [CERIDES Tweet: METICOS participates in P2PKOS event \(left\)](#)

Figure 33 [NTUA \(ICCS\) Facebook post: METICOS newsletter \(right\)](#)

Figure 34 [VIL Facebook post: METICOS participates in FRONTEX event \(left\)](#)

Figure 35 [NetU LinkedIn post: METICOS participates in the CCI conference \(right\)](#)

3.5 External events and meetings

3.5.1 Past events

During this reporting period, the partners participated in 7 external events:

1. [Second Secure Societies “Project to policy kick-off Seminar”](#).

Date: 22-23 of March 2021 | **Location:** Online | **Attended by** the European University Cyprus

METICOS Project virtually attended the Second Secure Societies “Project to policy kick-off seminar” (P2PKOS) organised by the EC and Research Executive Agency (REA). It included participation from 43 projects of the 2019 H2020 Secure Societies call, as well as representatives from the REA, DG HOME (Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs), DG CNECT (Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology), additional EC policy officers and other European agency representatives.

During Day 1 of the 2-day event, a series of speakers provided information and guidelines on subjects such as ‘Crisis Communications for EU security research’, ‘The challenge of Innovation Uptake’, as well as to be introduced into the ‘the Horizon Results Booster’. During Day 2, the METICOS representatives had the opportunity to present the project and discuss with the Policy Officers the scope of METICOS and the technology to be used.

Figure 36 METICOS participation in P2PKOS

2. [European Migration Network \(EMN\) Event](#)

Date: 24 of March 2021 | **Location:** Online | **Attended by** the European University Cyprus

The European Migration Network (EMN) is an EU network of migration and asylum experts who work together to provide objective, comparable policy-relevant information and knowledge on emerging issues relating to asylum and migration in Europe. In this respect, METICOS, together with the cluster project PERSONA gave a joint presentation of the Member States' National Contact Points of the European Migration Network (EMN). Additional info about EMN can be found [here](#).

Figure 37 EMN event

3. [METICOS participating in a closed workshop organised by FRONTEX](#)

Date: 20-21 of May 2021 | **Location:** Online | **Attended by** the European University Cyprus

On 20-21 May 2021, [Frontex](#) held a workshop to discuss ongoing border security projects in the EU Horizon framework. The activity aimed to familiarise the European Border and Coast Guard (EBCG) community with selected Research and Innovation projects and to provide feedback from an operational perspective.

The event brought together experts from 17 Member States and Schengen Associated Countries, numerous Frontex staff, and experts representing industry, academia, NGOs, research centres and end-users (e.g. ministries of interior, police directorates, etc.). In addition, DG Home, the Joint Research Centre and the Research Executive Agency were also present and actively contributed to the discussions.

As part of the workshop, participants learned about the scope and objectives of newly launched projects (BorderUAS, EFFECTOR, ISOLA, iMARS, ITFLOWS and METICOS). They discussed the ongoing activities (ARESIBO, COMPASS2020, ANDROMEDA, BorderSens and D4FLY).

The Project Coordinator of METICOS, Pantelis Velanas, presented METICOS to the European Border and Coast Guard community going through the scope and focus of the project and plans.

Figure 38 METICOS Participation in EBCG workshop

4. [METICOS at the European Association for Biometrics and the Research Projects Conference](#)

Date: 13-15 September 2021 | **Location:** Online | **Attended by** the European University Cyprus and ViLabs representatives

The 8th edition of the EAB Research Projects Conference took place virtually from 13 to 15 September 2021. The conference was organised by the [European Association on Biometrics \(EAB\)](#) in cooperation with the [Joint Research Center \(DG JRC\) of the European Commission](#), through its Cyber and Digital Citizens' security Unit.

The conference was the largest EU funded event on research in the area of Biometrics and Identity Management. Over the previous successful editions, EAB-RPC has become the main forum in Europe where attendees can simultaneously: promote research carried out in biometrics, forge new links and networks, and identify the appropriate partners for possible future project applications. Last year's edition welcomed over 100 participants from academia, industry, and public institutions.

On the 14th of September, the 2nd day of the conference, METICOS representatives participated in the event and presented the overall project and expected outcomes, focusing on the evaluation of technology and assessment of the performance of biometric systems.

In addition, it has to be mentioned that our partners and members of the H2020 BES Cluster, TRESSPASS, D4FLY, IT-FLOWS, and iMARS also attended the conference and presented their current progress and results. The agenda of the conference can be found [here](#).

Figure 39 Poster and meeting agenda

5. METICOS in the CCI Conference: Designing Security Futures

Date: 24–25 of November 2021 | **Location:** Brussels, Belgium | **Participating projects:** [PREVISION](#), [TRACE](#), [PROTAX](#), [LAW-GAME](#), [DARLENE](#), [SHOTROPS](#), [EFUS](#), [IOM UN migration](#)

On the 24th and 25th of November, METICOS, represented by the Project Coordinator Pantelis Velanas and the dissemination team, had the opportunity to participate in the Final Conference: “Designing Security Futures” of the [Cutting Crime Impact](#) H2020 Project, receiving information about the project activities and outputs of the project. METICOS also had the opportunity to share information about the project, its’ activities, and partners, as well as about the H2020 BES Cluster and its’ members. The 2-day conference, was a great opportunity for networking with the other participants as well as the other exhibitors, exploring grounds of collaboration and mutual support.

This event included presentations, discussions, and workshops exploring human-centred approaches to innovating security solutions and ways of integrating different strategies across EU contexts.

250 participants attended the event, and METICOS is now in contact with 180 of them. METICOS agreed to explore potential ways of collaboration with the exhibitors from the conference. This event gave a networking opportunity for further joint communication activities

Figure 40 Snapshots from the CCI final event

6. Northern Lights Deep Learning Conference 2022

Date: 10-11 of January 2022 | **Location:** Tromsø, Norway | **Attended by** NTNU

Deep learning is an emerging subfield in machine learning that has achieved state-of-the-art performance in image classification, object detection, segmentation, time series prediction, and speech recognition, to name a few. This conference gathered researchers on a national and international level to exchange ideas, encourage collaborations, and present cutting-edge research.

In the context of this conference, representatives from METICOS partner NTNU hosted two sessions on the 11th of January. The first session was on "Deep learning for Cultural Heritage" with two different subtopics: a) Automated mapping of cultural heritage in Norway from airborne lidar data using faster R-CNN, and b) Semantic Aware Style Transfer: Preserving Artistry Relevance. The second was an oral session with two topics: a) Expert Q-learning: Deep Reinforcement Learning with Coarse State Values from Offline Expert Examples, and b) Deep Reinforcement Learning for Detection of Abnormal Anatomies.

Figure 41 Event agenda

7. ERCIM FP Community Event

Date: 10-11 of January 2022 | **Location:** Online | **Attended by** NTNU

ERCIM ([European Research Consortium for Informatics and Mathematics](https://ercim.eu)) aims to foster collaborative work within the European research community and to increase cooperation with European industry. It organised an online community event for its fellows and guests, attended by 52 participants to present their work, exchange ideas, and get to know each other. The main goal of this virtual event was to encourage interaction among fellows and reassure them that they are part of the same community.

The centrepiece of the event was a poster session. It illustrated the fellows' outstanding scientific work and helped identify common research challenges even in different fields. As an alumnus of the ERCIM Fellowship Program, METICOS colleague Erjon Zoto from NTNU was invited as a speaker during this event. He introduced the METICOS project, its main objectives, and activities during his keynote speech.

ERCIM FP Community Event 9 November 2021 Online via Gather.town	
AGENDA	
Time in UTC+1.	
08:30 to 08:55	Online Arrival.
09:00 to 09:10	Welcome (Keynote Room).
09:15 to 09:45	Poster session (Poster Room A) <i>All fellows whose poster number begins with A must be in front of their poster within the allotted time.</i>
09:50 to 10:20	Poster session (Poster Room B) <i>All fellows whose poster number begins with B must be in front of their poster within the allotted time.</i>
10:25 to 10:55	Poster session (Poster Room C) <i>All fellows whose poster number begins with C must be in front of their poster within the allotted time.</i>
11:00 to 11:30	Poster session (Poster Room D) <i>All fellows whose poster number begins with D must be in front of their poster within the allotted time.</i>
11:30 to 11:40	Break for discussion.
11:45 to 12:15	"Data, privacy, ethics: context for research" (Keynote Room). Speaker: Gabriel David (INESC)
12:20 to 12:30	Experience of previous ERCIM fellows (5 minutes each) (Keynote room). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ass. Prof. Erjon zoto (Assistant Professor at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)) • Dr. Audrius Jurgelionis (Fullstack Developer at Swisscom).
12:35 to 12:40:	Closure presentation (Keynote Room).
12:45 to 13:00	Break for discussion.

Figure 42 ERCIM FP Community Event agenda

3.5.2 Upcoming events

METICOS partners have confirmed their participation in two upcoming events for the next reporting period:

1. [2022 World Border Security Congress](#)

Date: 17– 19 of May 2022 | **Location:** Lisbon, Portugal | **To be attended** by ITPFT

The World Border Security Congress is the premier multi-jurisdictional transnational platform where the border protection, management, and security industry policymakers and practitioners convene to discuss the international challenges faced in protecting borders. The topic of this conference will be “Developing Border Strategies Through Co-operation and Technology”.

METICOS partner ITPFT will attend this event to present a paper on the topic of “Ever seething Balkans: Effects of Irregular Migration on Border Security”. The paper has been accepted to be presented during the Congress.

Figure 43 World Security Congress: Iliuta Cumpanasu among the key speakers

2. Computing Conference 2022

Date: 14–15 of July 2022 | **Location:** London, UK | **To be attended** by NTNU

The Computing Conference will feature keynote talks, special sessions, poster presentations, tutorials, workshops, and contributed papers each year. The conference's goal is to be a premier venue for researchers and industry practitioners to share new ideas, research results, and development experiences in various fields. It is one of the most respected conferences in the area of computer science. The presentations include:

- Talks by industry experts on the state-of-the-art in computer science
- Lectures by eminent scientists designed to inspire and inform
- Presentations by innovative researchers coming from 50+ countries
- Discussion-oriented sessions and networking breaks to enable collaborations

METICOS colleagues from NTNU have submitted a paper to present at this conference. The title is **“A survey of artificial intelligence techniques for user perceptions”**, and it was accepted to be presented during the conference.

Figure 44 Computing conference 2022

(More information about the scientific publications is presented in section 3.6)

3.5.3 Related events

METICOS is constantly looking for new opportunities for networking and knowledge exchange with other projects and initiatives at the national, European, or international levels. In this regard, the project website hosts a page dedicated to upcoming third-party events/conferences related to the METICOS area of interest.

A plethora of activities regarding the developments on migration, border control, and relative topics are taking place worldwide. Such events offer METICOS and H2020 BES Cluster a significant opportunity to disseminate activities and results. Thus, METICOS proceeded with listing the events organised by international agencies, fora, and institutions around the domain that METICOS covers.

The list is constantly being updated. So far, 19 events have been listed. The list is available on the project website, under "[Related events](#)".

Third-party events/conferences related to METICOS Project and activities!

Conference Title	Date	Location
ICBSDS: Border Security and Defense Studies	7-8 February 2022	Amsterdam, Netherlands
ICBSI: Border Security and Immigration	15-16 February 2022	London, United Kingdom
ICBSSM: Border Security Studies and Migration	18-19 February 2022	Rome, Italy
ICBSS: Border Security Studies	15-16 March 2022	London, United Kingdom
ICBSS: Border Security Solutions	22-23 March 2022	Istanbul, Turkey
ICBSS: Border Security and Systems	22-23 March 2022	Prague, Czech Republic
ICTBM: Borders and Migration	29-30 March 2022	Paris, France
ICBSSMC: Border Security Studies and Migration Crisis	8-9 April 2022	Rome, Italy
ICBSM: Border Security and Migration	26-27 April 2022	Istanbul, Turkey
ICBSS: Border Security and Systems	24-25 May 2022	Barcelona, Spain
ICBCSA: Border Control Systems and Applications	10-11 June 2022	Barcelona, Spain
20th International Conference on Practical Applications of Agents and Multi-Agent Systems	13-15 July 2022	Italy, Hybrid
ICBCSA: Border Control Systems and Applications	19-20 July 2022	Helsinki, Finland
ICMBS: Migration and Border Studies	22-23 July 2022	Rome, Italy
ICBSA: Border Security and Applications	16-17 August 2022	Venice, Italy
ICMBS: Migration and Border Studies	30-31 August 2022	Rome, Italy
ICBSSST: Border Security Systems and Technologies	30-31 August 2022	Budapest, Hungary
ICABS: Applications of Border Security	30-31 August 2022	Paris, France
ICASBBHR: Administrative Science, Blockading the Border and Human Rights	15-16 September 2022	Amsterdam, Netherlands

Figure 45 METICOS related events

3.6 Scientific publications

As project activities progress and draw from project partners' previous and created knowledge, a series of scientific articles are going to be published in the international scientific literature in the upcoming project period. All partners acknowledge their shared interest in publishing the knowledge to obtain recognition and advance the state of knowledge in the field. Especially when the content of the publication is a product of the collective work of the Consortium (or of a sub-group of partners), the names of the respective people and partners will appear on the publication. The Consortium will respect Article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement with regards to “Open access to scientific publications”. Each beneficiary will ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

METICOS Consortium in line with the expected plan, have successfully submitted three scientific papers:

1. ***“Towards Understanding of User Perceptions for Smart Border Control Technologies using a Fine-Tuned Transformer Approach.”***

Authors: Sarang Shaikh, Sule Yildirim Yayilgan, Erjon Zoto, Mohamed Abomhara.

In the context of the [Northern Lights Deep Learning Conference \(NLDL\)](#), representatives from NTNU have submitted their paper. It was presented during the Conference, and now it is under review to be officially published.

Abstract: Smart Border Control (SBC) technologies became a hot topic in recent years when the European Union (EU) Commission announced the Smart Borders Package to improve the efficiency and security of the border crossing points (BCPs). Although BCPs technologies have potential benefits in terms of enabling traveller’ data processing, they still lead to acceptability and usability challenges when used by travellers. The success of technologies depends on user acceptance. Sentiment analysis is one of the primary techniques to measure user acceptance. Although, there exists a variety of studies in literature where sentiment analysis has been used to understand user acceptance in different domains. To the best of our knowledge, there is no study where sentiment analysis has been used for measuring the user acceptance of SBC technologies. Thus, in this study, we propose a fine-tuned transformer model and an automatic sentiment labels generation technique to perform sentiment analysis to get insights into user acceptance of BCPs technologies. The results obtained in this study are promising, given the condition that there is no training data available from BCPs. The proposed approach was validated against the IMDB reviews dataset and achieved a weighted F1-score of 79% for the sentiment analysis task.

Below you can find the poster of their presentation:

NTNU
Norwegian University of Science and Technology

Towards Understanding of User Perceptions for Smart Border Control Technologies using a Fine-Tuned Transformer Approach

Sarang Shaikh¹, Sule Yildirim Yayilgan¹, Erjon Zoto¹, Mohamed Abomhara¹
¹Dept. Of Information Security and Communication Technology (IIK), Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Gjøvik, Norway

Abstract

- **Smart Border Control (SBC) technologies** is a hot topic in recent years.
- **Smart Borders Package** was introduced by European Union (EU) Commission.
- **Acceptability and usability challenges** are the major challenges faced by these technologies.
- **Sentiment Analysis** is a primary technique to measure user acceptance.
- **Existing gap:** there is no existing study available where sentiment analysis used for measuring the user acceptance of SBC technologies. Also, no existing sentiments labelled dataset available for SBC technologies.
- **Objective of this study** is to propose a fine-tuned transformer model along with an automatic sentiment labels generation technique to perform sentiment analysis as a step towards getting insights into user acceptance of BCPs technologies.

Introduction and Background

- **SBC technologies** are fully or semi-automated technologies with the purpose of verifying traveller’s identity without any human (i.e., border guard) intervention [1]. Despite the potential benefits of the SBC technologies at BCPs, users (i.e. travellers) perceptions of acceptability of the technologies may change with actual experience of users with them.
- We have a focus on finding out the reasons for:
 - why acceptance of SBC technologies depend on user perceptions,
 - changes in user perceptions for SBC technologies, and
 - changes in user perceptions after users have actual experience with SBC technologies.
- through questionnaires and social media data analysis

Table 1. State-of-the-art studies for extracting user perceptions from social media data

Authors	Social Media Platform	Data	Perceptions	Technique	Type	Results
Khan et. al. [2]	Yelp	Yelp Challenge Dataset (2835065 user reviews)	Rating perceptions to restaurants, ecommerce	Users Rating Classification using Machine Learning (NaiveBayes, RandomForest, DecisionTree, SVM, KNN, MLP)	Supervised	96% NaiveBayes
Xuan et. al. [3]	Facebook	Facebook Posts (37426 in health, technology, travel, finance, sports)	Users interests and trends (i.e. health, tech, travel, sports)	Users Trends Classification using Machine Learning (NaiveBayes, DecisionTree, SVM), Deep Learning (CNN)	Supervised	91% CNN
Alshamrani et. al. [4]	Twitter	Tweets (26 million b/w 01/10/2019 and 30/04/2020)	users behaviours and trends before and after COVID-19	Deep Learning for Sentiment Analysis (DNN, CNN, LSTM, BERT), LDA for Topic Modeling	Supervised	87% BERT
Rosario et. al. [5]	Twitter and surveys	N/A	users experiences and perceptions for e-learning tools	Deep Learning (CNN, BiLSTM, Transformers), Google, Microsoft APIs	Supervised	61.7% Transformer
Molinari et. al. [6]	Twitter	Tweets (13800 related to URBAN-GEO BIG DATA sensing)	Investigate citizens perceptions of mobility services for urban geo sensing	Machine Learning (NaiveBayes)	Supervised	N/A

Methods and Materials

Figure 1. The Proposed Methodology

Table 2. Datasets

Primary dataset	SBC tweets
Validation dataset	IMDB reviews

Figure 2. SBC tweets distribution per query

Table 3. Hyperparameters of the proposed BERT model

# of epochs	10
Training batch size	16
Validation batch size	64
Learning rate	1e-4
Optimizer	Adam
Warmup steps	500

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<https://meticos-project.eu>

smouldered for a long time, waiting just for a good moment to implode. The findings of the study are therefore able to capture an area that has not yet benefitted from a comprehensive approach in the scientific community, such as the concept of “Memory Effect” in irregular migration, the Seasonality, Victims or Business Partners’?, between migration variables, etc., also highlighting how the recent ‘Pandemic’ interfered with border management.

Moreover, due to the high external validity and generalisability of the research, the results of the study are intended for use by policy and decision-makers at international, regional, or national levels when analysing, drafting, or implementing public policies or strategies in the fields of border security and migration management.

The scientific outcomes of this study were validated on June 30, 2021, when the author defended his dissertation for the European Joint Master’s in Strategic Border Management, a prestigious two-year program supported by the European Commission and Frontex Agency, and a Consortium of six European Universities.

Figure 47 World Border Security Congress

3. “A survey of artificial intelligence techniques for user perceptions’ extraction from social media data”

Authors: Sarang Shaikh, Sule Yildirim Yayilgan, Erjon Zoto, Mohamed Abomhara.

During the [Computing Conference 2022](#) on 14 and 15 of July, representatives from NTNU will present their paper.

Abstract: Measuring and analysing user perceptions and behaviours to make user-centric decisions has been a research topic for a long time, even before the invention of social media platforms. In the past, the main approaches for measuring user perceptions were conducting surveys, interviewing experts, and collecting data through questionnaires. But the main challenge with these methods was that the extracted perceptions were only able to represent a small group of people and not the whole public. This challenge was resolved when social media platforms like Twitter and Facebook were introduced, and users started to share their perceptions about any product, topic, or event using these platforms. As these platforms became popular, the amount of data being shared on these platforms

started to grow exponentially, and this growth led to another challenge of analysing this huge amount of data to understand or measure user perceptions. Computational techniques are used to address the challenge. This paper briefly describes the artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, which is one of the types of computational techniques available for analysing social media data. Along with brief information about the AI techniques, this paper also shows state-of-the-art studies that utilise the AI techniques to measure user perceptions from social media data.

Conference Tracks			
Technology Trends <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internet of Things Blockchain Cyber-Physical Systems Big Data Smart Cities Machine to Machine Data Analytics Mobile Applications Digital Transformation Social Computing 	Computing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantum Computing High Performance Computing Distributed and parallel systems Cognitive Computing Cloud Computing Grid Computing Embedded Computing Scalable Computing Human-centred Computing Mobile computing 	Artificial Intelligence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deep Learning Neural Networks Fuzzy Logic Expert Systems Agents and Multi-agent Systems Natural Language Processing Data Mining Computational Optimization Robotics Sentiment Analysis 	Machine Vision <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human Computer Interaction Computer Vision Image Processing Brain-Machine Interface Geographic Information Systems Video Analysis Medical Diagnosis Segmentation Techniques Augmented Reality Virtual Reality
Security <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Privacy Surveillance Biometrics Internet Security Intrusion Detection Web Services and Performance Secure Transactions Cryptography Secure Protocols Cyber Security 	Communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connected Machines Networking Wireless/ Mobile Communication Signal Processing Satellite Communication Systems 4G/5G Network Evolutions Mobile Adhoc Networks Open Spectrum Solutions Communication Protocols Cognitive Radio 	Ambient Intelligence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Cities Smart Grids and Energy Networks Sensing and Sensor Networks Ambient Assisted Living Smart Healthcare Intelligent Transportation Data Science Affective computing Agents and Multi-agent Systems Context-aware pervasive systems 	e-Learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> e-Learning Tools Mobile Learning e-Learning Organisational Issues Gamification Collaborative Learning Curriculum Content Desig Educational Systems Design Virtual Learning Environments Web-based Learning Delivery Systems and Environments

Figure 48 Conference tracks – topics

3.7 Potential cooperation for communication and dissemination activities

Taking advantage of the participation in the CCI event, METICOS opened communication channels with relevant projects and initiatives. Below is a list of these actors (Table 2):

	<p>PREVISION partners will take advantage of their capabilities, expertise, and previously delivered research, together with already defined and emerging standards and best practices in Europe, to focus their resources and attention on the project's new elements and novel aspects. The overall strategy is based on an iterative development methodology, which involves frequent software releases being made available to the LEA and practitioners end-users for testing and evaluation.</p>
	<p>TRACE project will explore the rise and spread of ICT-enabled crimes and illicit financial flows (IFFs). Considering that innovative policing tools are required to patrol the virtual routes, the project will focus on new ways to identify, track and document IFFs. In consultation with law enforcement agencies, the project will apply its solutions in use cases on terrorist financing, web forensics, cyber extortion, and</p>

	the use of cryptocurrencies in money laundering in arts and antiquities, and online gambling.
	<p>PRO TAX generates policy guidelines and toolkits to harmonise the treatment of tax crime and enhance information sharing across different European jurisdictions. The consortium includes researchers, law enforcement agencies, and national tax authorities from several EU countries.</p>
	<p>LAW-GAME trains police officers on the procedure, enhancing the transition between the theory and real-life practice through gamification technologies in a safe and controlled virtual environment.</p>
	<p>DARLENE is a three-year EU funded project investigating how cutting-edge augmented reality (AR) technology can be deployed to help law enforcement agencies (LEAs) and first responders make more informed and rapid decisions especially in situations where time is of the essence. The project develops innovative augmented reality (AR) tools that aim to improve situational awareness when responding to criminal and terrorist activities.</p>
	<p>EFUS (European Forum for Urban Security) is the only European network dedicated to fostering discussion, cooperation, and support among local and regional authorities in the field of crime prevention and urban security. Founded in 1987, it brings together nearly 250 cities and regions from 15 countries.</p>
	<p>CoP (Community Policing without borders) inspires the Belgian police force, to contribute to the eradication of all forms of racism, xenophobia, and other forms of intolerance and discrimination within the Belgian Police force and by the Belgian police towards migrant communities.</p>

Table 2 Potential cooperation for joint communication activities

4. Synergies with other projects and initiatives

4.1 H2020 BES Cluster Community

METICOS has put great effort into the engagement of relevant stakeholders creating strategic partnerships. Having a strong consortium, well-known in the European community, the project has implemented a series of joint activities with the so-called “H2020 BES Cluster Community” consisting of projects funded under the H2020 framework. Currently, the Cluster counts 11 members (METICOS included). Furthermore, it continues to participate in jointed efforts and campaigns with other projects and initiatives, to engage the targeted stakeholders. The aim of these synergies is double:

Firstly, to exchange information relevant to communication and dissemination and support each other with these activities.

Secondly, to exchange ideas on good practices and methodologies, explore possibilities and opportunities to combine pilots’ activities, and work on future policy suggestions. Finally, the sustainability/exploitation impact of the projects is also highly essential, and it is better if we collaborate with other EU projects to find and propose practical measures for evidence-informed policy suggestions.

4.1.1 Strategy

The projects participating in the H2020 BES Cluster community aim to address similar issues in the area of border and external security of research and innovation. Also, they have the opportunity to exchange knowledge about their methodologies and conclude with policy suggestions. This cooperation creates a common repository that can be used as a valuable source of information and inspiration for other external stakeholders.

The construction of the cluster is an ongoing process, and METICOS is constantly looking for new projects and initiatives that would like to join. The cluster organises collaborative actions such as events and conferences on relevant topics. Each project participating in the cluster is responsible for disseminating these actions through its communication channels.

METICOS has created a dedicated section on the project website under the menu “Synergies” → “H2020 BES Cluster”. Also, the communication manager creates relevant communication material for the online channels, emphasising the collaborative character of the events.

4.1.2 Members

At the moment, the cluster counts 11 members (METICOS included). On Twitter, the relevant posts are accompanied by the #H2020BESCluster.

Figure 49 H2020 BES Cluster members

[TRESSPASS](#) is a European research project in the H2020 framework and Border and External Security thematic area, receiving EU funding under GA 787120. The overall scope of TRESSPASS is to modernise the way the security checks at border crossing points (BCPs) are held out at land, air, and sea. TRESSPASS imports the concept of “risk-based” security checks and proposes an analytic framework for modelling risk as well as a systematic approach of quantifying risk, based on a set of indicators ranging from real-time behaviour analytics to intelligent information extraction and sharing that can accurately be measured across all four tiers of the EU Integrated Border Management:

- (1) measures undertaken in, or jointly with third countries or service providers;
- (2) cooperation with neighbouring countries;
- (3) border control and counter-smuggling measures, and
- (4) control measures within the area of free movement.

[MIRROR](#) aims to develop an integrated platform, a set of tools, as well as a systematic methodology for the comprehensive inter-media analysis of the perception of Europe, the detection of discrepancies between the perception of and reality in Europe, and the creation of awareness for the impact of such misconceptions.

The multidisciplinary consortium consists of fourteen partners from seven countries from research and industry, as well as practitioners. The consortium will cooperate to better understand how Europe is perceived abroad and the mechanisms involved in the process. The MIRROR Project was launched in June 2019 and has a period of three years.

ITFLOWS will generate novel insights on migration. The purpose of ITFLOWS is to provide accurate predictions and adequate management solutions of migration flow in the European Union in the phases of reception, relocation, settlement, and integration of migration, according to a wide range of human factors and using multiple sources of information. These insights will be provided by an evidence-based ICT enabled solution (the EUMigraTool) and precise models. All solutions will have fitness for purpose continually validated by policy-makers and practitioners in cooperation with civil society organisations in a dynamic and iterative process.

ITFLOWS will propose tailor-made solutions for practitioners and policymakers for managing migration. On the one hand, the EUMigraTool targets first-line practitioners, second-level reception organisations, and municipalities. It will provide modular solutions based on the prediction of migration flows and the identification of risks of tensions between migrants and EU citizens. On the other hand, an in-depth analysis of drivers, patterns, and choices of migration as well as public sentiment towards migration will lead to the drafting of adequate recommendations and good practices for policymakers, governments and EU institutions.

PERCEPTIONS

PERCEPTIONS examines how Europe and the EU are seen by people who have immigrated there or intend to do so. It examines what perceptions of Europe exist among this group, how they are formed, whether they correspond to reality, and how they influence migration decisions. **PERCEPTIONS** also examines how the flow of information could be distorted and whether inaccurate information could lead to a threat to the security of migrants (e.g. through dangerous border crossings) or even national security (e.g. radicalisation).

PERSONA project has been brought into being to come up with a unified and tailored Impact Assessment Method for No-Gate Crossing Point Solutions capable of appropriately evaluating border controlling technologies and of ensuring that these solutions meet the requirements and expectations of governments, LEAS, and border crossing individuals.

EFFECTOR aims to enhance maritime surveillance, improve decisions support, and foster collaboration of maritime stakeholders by implementing an Interoperability Framework and associated Data Fusion and Analytics services for Maritime Surveillance and Border Security that will allow faster detection of new events, better-informed decision making, achievement of a joint understanding and undertaking of a situation across borders, allowing seamless cooperation between operating authorities and on-site intervention forces ensuring that all existing privacy and data protection rules are fully respected. Specifically, **EFFECTOR** will unlock the full capabilities of maritime surveillance systems and data sharing at a tactical and strategic level by introducing applied solutions for enhanced border and external security, including the implementation of a multilayered data lake platform for end-to-end interoperability and data exploitation, the exchange of enhanced situational awareness pictures at a different level with CISE and EUROSUR, the adoption of interoperability standards for exploiting data sources and systems currently underutilised in the maritime environment and the demonstration of new concepts and tools for knowledge extraction, semantic representation, data

fusion, analytics, and federated querying that can scale from local to regional and up to national and transnational level.

[D4FLY](#) identifies, reduces, and avoids vulnerabilities in the identity lifecycle of modern border management, thereby strengthening European Smart Borders against serious and organised crime. It does this by exploring, developing, and validating new technologies for identity and document verification – including biometrics-on-the-fly, and even explores how this could work in risk-based border management concepts.

The D4FLY project will augment the current capabilities and capacities of border authorities in countering emerging threats in document and identity verification (e.g., forged documents, impostor fraud, morphed faces) at manual and highly automated border control points and in the issuance process of genuine documents.

In [BORDERUAS](#), nineteen (19) organisations from twelve (12) European countries joined forces for a new technology project that enhances border and external security. The project will combine for the first time a multi-role lighter-than-air (LTA) unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) with an ultra-high resolution multi-sensor surveillance payload supporting border surveillance, search & rescue applications, and specifically rough terrain detection.

[iMARS](#) project aims to provide image morphing and manipulation attack detection solutions for the evaluation of ID document authenticity, ID document verification, and fraud detection. iMARS will deliver mobile tools to check document integrity. The technology will be assessed from an ethical, legal, and societal perspective, and validated in real border control conditions. iMARS will support the standardisation of these solutions and their evaluation protocols and will provide training, guidelines, and best practices to border guards, document investigators, and passport application officers.

[ROBORDER](#) aims at developing and demonstrating a fully functional autonomous border surveillance system with unmanned mobile robots including aerial, water surface, underwater, and ground vehicles which will incorporate multimodal sensors as part of an interoperable network. The project intends to implement a heterogeneous robot system and enhance it with detection capabilities for early identification of criminal activities at border and coastal areas along with marine pollution events.

4.1.3 Activities Reporting

4.1.3.1 Promotion through cluster's communication channels and EU level stakeholders

The projects participating in the H2020BESCluster₇ enhance the visibility of each other, using their communication channels. In this regard, the projects share news about other projects in the cluster, using their websites and social media accounts. Also, METICOS has been mentioned by EU level stakeholders such as [FRONTEX](#) and the [European Association Biometrics](#) (EAB). Sample posts of these promotional activities are displayed below:

1. METICOS on BES Cluster projects' websites

Figure 50 METICOS on TRESSPASS website (left)

Figure 51 METICOS on BorderUAS website (right)

Figure 52 METICOS on iMARS website (left)

Figure 53 METICOS on PERSONA website (right)

Figure 54 METICOS on EFFECTOR website

2. METICOS on BES Cluster projects' social media

BES Cluster on LinkedIn

Figure 55 EFFECTOR post about the BES Cluster (left)

Figure 56 iMARS post about their collaboration with METICOS (right)

Figure 57 ITFLOWS and EFFECTOR posts about the BES Cluster event

Figure 58 TRESSPASS and EFFECTOR posts about their collaboration with METICOS

BES Cluster on Twitter

EFFECTOR_H2020 @effector_h2020 · Nov 25, 2021
 Congrats 🎉 to our synergy 🤝 project @MeticosEU, and @CCIproject for their joint dissemination activities !! Keep up the great work!
 #H2020BESCluster

↳ **METICOS EU** @MeticosEU · Nov 24, 2021
 Together with the dissemination manager of @CCIproject in their final conference.
 #meticos #h2020bescluster #joiningdisseminationforces

CCI Project @CCIproject · Nov 25, 2021
 Meet some of our beautiful exhibitors of the #CCIconference 🥰🥰🥰
 @H2020Prevision @TRACEH2020 @PROTAX2020 @MeticosEU @LawGame_EUH2020 @Efusnews

↳ **METICOS EU** @MeticosEU · Nov 25, 2021
 The exhibitors of @CCIproject final conference team-up!! Follow us and find out more about our projects!
 @MeticosEU #H2020BESCluster @LawGame_EUH2020 @Efusnews @TRACEH2020 @H2020Prevision @PROTAX2020

SHOTPROS @shotpros · Nov 8, 2021
 #SHOTPROS is pleased to contribute to the #CCIconference on the 24th and 25th of November in Brussels!
 Learn more ➡ cuttingcrimeimpact.eu/news-events/ev...
 @CCIproject @KU_Leuven @CampusVesta @MeticosEU @DarleneProject @H2020Prevision @PROTAX2020 @TRACEH2020 @LawGame_EUH2020 @Efusnews

Law-Game H2020 EU Project @LawGame_EUH2020 · Nov 12, 2021
 Meet us in #Brussels on 24&25 November at the closing event of the #CCIProject. Pleased to be among @PROTAX2020 @H2020Prevision @shotpros @MeticosEU @TRACEH2020 @DarleneProject @Efusnews @EU_Commission @CORDIS_EU

CCI Project @CCIproject · Nov 11, 2021
 It is with great pleasure that we announce the EU-funded projects and organisations that will be exhibiting at the #CCIconference.
 📍 Register and get the opportunity to meet them: bit.ly/CCI-Conference
 Show this thread

Figure 59 EFFECTOR, CCI, SHOTPROS and Law-Game tweets for the CCI event referring METICOS

Figure 60 D4FLY, iMARS and EFFECTOR tweets about collaborating with METICOS

Figure 61 EFFECTOR tweet about the 1st BES Cluster event

3. METICOS in BES Cluster projects’ newsletters:

Another communication channel is the newsletters. Below there are three examples of METICOS, featuring cluster projects’ newsletters.

Figure 62 METICOS in EFFECTOR newsletter (left)

Figure 63 METICOS in D4FLY newsletter (right)

Figure 64 METICOS in Border UAS newsletter

4. METICOS promoting other cluster projects:

On the other hand, the METICOS project also supports the activities of the cluster projects and uses its accounts to promote them. An example was the final event of the MIRROR project, that METICOS promoted through its social media (figure 65):

Figure 65 METICOS promoting Mirror Final Event on social media

5. METICOS on EU level stakeholders' communication channels

Figure 66 METICOS presented on EU level stakeholders' communication channels (EAB, FRONTEx)

4.1.3.2 Joint events reporting

During this reporting period, METICOS participated in a series of events with the cluster projects, both online and on-site.

1. [1st H2020 BES Cluster teleconference](#)

Date: 19 of May 2021 | **Location:** Online | **Participating cluster projects:** TRESSPASS, MIRROR, ITFLOWS, PERCEPTIONS, and EFFECTOR

The Project coordinators and/or Dissemination leaders of the cluster projects, organised their first e-meeting to establish a joint dissemination & knowledge exchange task force. The meeting was attended by nine people/project representatives. They had a brainstorming session and discussed the different ways the consortia can collaborate and set the targets for the upcoming period.

Figure 67 Snapshot from the H2020 BES Cluster teleconference

2. [1st EFFECTOR Workshop – 21st May 2021](#)

Date: 26 of May 2021 | **Location:** Online | **Organised by:** EFFECTOR

The first EFFECTOR workshop was held virtually, where the consortium shared its produced results and collected valuable feedback for project's next steps. As the project progresses into its second half, this online workshop gathered around 100 attendees. The end-users, and academic and industry representatives from the consortium presented the project and discussed the results achieved so far regarding the EFFECTOR Interoperability Framework for Maritime Situational Awareness.

1 st EFFECTOR Workshop, Virtual event	
Day I – 26, May, 2021	
Timeslot	Presentation
09:45 – 10:00	Arrival/Connection
10:00 – 10:05	Welcome to the 1 st EFFECTOR Workshop
Session 1: EFFECTOR Project Introduction	
10:05 – 10:25	EFFECTOR Project overview
Session 2: EFFECTOR Interoperability Framework for Maritime Situational Awareness	
10:25 – 11:05	EFFECTOR System & Semantically-enabled Data Lakes
11:05 – 11:45	EFFECTOR Heterogeneous Data Sources
11:45 – 12:25	EFFECTOR Interoperability & information exchange
Session 3: EFFECTOR Innovation Potential	
12:25 – 13:05	EFFECTOR Innovation Presentation
Closing 1st EFFECTOR Workshop	
13:05 – 13:20	Next steps in the EFFECTOR project Summary and closing remarks

Figure 68 1st EFFECTOR Workshop & agenda

3. [METICOS at the Piraeus Cruise Port as an Observer of TRESSPASS Demo activities](#)

Date: 22-23 of July 2021 | **Location:** Athens, Greece | **Organised by:** TRESSPASS

Representatives of METICOS participated as observers in the demonstration activities of the [Sea Pilot in Greece](#), which was organised by the TRESSPASS Project. The pilot attended approximately 30 people.

METICOS participated and observed the situation and travellers' interaction/perception in real seaport border crossing points and with real travellers risk-based screening situations.

Via the demonstration of [TRESSPASS](#), the port operators and border authorities utilised better their existing infrastructure and facilities, increase their capacities and throughput by eliminating the dependencies based on the types of travellers, their origins, entries or exit types and improve their existing border and customs control processes with limited resources needed, without causing any delay to cruise ship passengers. Furthermore, since cruising comparatively with other transportation means is considered so far as a low-risk form of traveling and tourism and the traffic created at BCP's is high, one expected impact is the implementation of a none stop point control for security and border control (SBC), without any delay.

The participation of METICOS in this pilot can be considered as a unique opportunity to interact with the travellers and the border authorities and to begin collecting information about the acceptance of the novel no gate solution framework. The main objectives of METICOS participation in TRESSPASS pilot 3 were:

- To evaluate the provided enhanced situational awareness in terms of the timely and proper identification of potentially dangerous people and goods and prevent smuggling and human trafficking.
- To evaluate the risk-management coordination and cooperation between border control (passport/persons), customs (baggage/goods), and security in transport (pre-boarding security checks on persons and baggage);

- To evaluate the improvement of proposed solutions for remote detection of abnormal behaviours;
- To evaluate the improvement and the acceptance of border automated screening systems

Following these objectives, the METICOS project prepared a short questionnaire to collect feedback from the travelers and the authorities who participated in the TRESSPASS project.

Figure 69 Snapshot from the Piraeus Cruise Port pilot case of TRESSPASS

4.1.4 Upcoming activities

4.1.4.1 H2020 BES Cluster expansion

METICOS project will continue working on the expansion of the H2020 BES Cluster and invite more EU funded projects to join. As mentioned above, the METICOS representatives in the CCI final event, explored further collaboration with the exhibitors and participants there. In addition, the communication manager of the project has identified other potential members. These projects are listed below (table 3):

	<p>SHOTPROS aims to improve the training for European Police officers. The influence of psychological and contextual human factors (HFs) on the behaviour of decision-making and acting (DMA) of police officers under stress and in high-risk operational situations will be investigated. Based on the results, SHOTPROS will develop an HF-rooted training curriculum and a corresponding VR training solution to provide a comprehensive framework for practical training.</p>
	<p>MEDEA aims to engage a critical mass of security practitioners and actors including first aid responders, border guards, national police, civil protection teams, humanitarian workers, defence entities and other interested stakeholders in efficient cooperation with cross-discipline</p>

	entities from other countries. The expected result would be the effective response to all security threats common to the Mediterranean and Black Sea region.
	ALIGNER aims to bring together European actors concerned with Artificial Intelligence, Law Enforcement, and Policing to collectively identify and discuss needs for paving the way for a more secure Europe in which Artificial Intelligence supports LEAs while simultaneously empowering, benefit-ing, and protecting the public.
	ISOLA will develop, integrate, test, deploy, demonstrate and validate a systematic and fully automated security approach by incorporating innovative technologies for sensing, monitoring, data fusion, alarming and reporting real-time during illegal incidents. This will ensure high level of security among all the passengers of the ship and augmentation of the Ship Security Plan.

Table 3 Potential members of the H2020 BES cluster

4.1.4.2 Upcoming events

During the next reporting period, the BES Cluster is planning to organise joint activities to strengthen and broaden its network. First, the projects discuss the organisation of a physical event. Also, due to the nature of the projects, they have a high potential of organising joint pilot activities, or attend one another activities, to exchange knowledge and experience. Last, based on the common knowledge produced, they are planning to join forces to have a joint publication.

So far, two events organised by cluster projects have been added to METICOS calendar for 2022:

1. [MEDEA RDI Day for TCP 2: “Border management and Surveillance” on the 9th of March 2022](#)

The project focuses on four different thematic Communities of Practitioners (TCP), listed as follows:

- TCP 1: Management of Migration Flows and Asylum seekers
- TCP 2: Border management and Surveillance
- TCP 3: Cross border organised crime and terrorism
- TCP 4: Natural hazards and technological accidents

As part of engaging with a critical mass of security practitioners, MEDEA also holds RDI Days for each TCP to allow new technologies in this area to be presented to practitioners. These events give the floor to industries in order for them to present their technologies. During this event, METICOS will have the opportunity to present its innovative solution to relevant security practitioners and actors.

Figure 70 MEDEA Surveillance event

2. **SHOTPROS Final Conference** on the 14th and 15th of September 2022.

SHOTPROS is in its last year and this spring will deliver 5 Field Trials to validate the research that has been done on human factors and stress in relation to the VR product. LEAs from Austria, Romania, Germany, Belgium and the Netherlands will host a Field Trial in order to give their officers and management the chance to experience the VR solution. On 14-15 September 2022 they will hold their Final Conference in their training centre CAMPUS VESTA in Antwerp, Belgium. METICOS is in communication with the SHOTPROS consortium, and we have been invited to participate.

5. Monitoring and evaluation

The monitoring and evaluation of the METICOS dissemination activities is an essential task that is performed regularly, to provide concrete evidence on the effectiveness of dissemination, as well as insights on how to maximise its reach and impact. The communication manager has developed an online form on EU survey (presented in Annex I), that partners were requested to complete with their related dissemination actions. In addition, specific KPIs have been developed from the beginning of the project to allow comparisons between the planned and actual activities, as well as their effectiveness to reach their goals.

5.1 METICOS Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Communication tool	Target	Status – M18	Achieved/ Expecting
Project website	At least 5000 users will have accessed the website by the end of the project.	>1434 active users /7,247 Views/19,668 events	<i>Achieved and in progress</i>
Project brochures	500 copies or digital copies to be distributed throughout the project duration.	<i>Due to Covid-19 restrictions, all project activities were held online, hence there were no project brochures distributed. During the CCI Final conference that took place on November 2021, 200 copies have been distributed.</i>	<i>Achieved</i>
Organisation of presentation / feedback sessions at major forums or trade shows, relevant to the project theme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 in total - Attendance of 40-70 delegates. 	>3	<i>Achieved</i>
A series of data security applications developers training to METICOS solutions	Attendance of 20-30 delegates, including representatives from the METICOS end-users	-	<i>Expected</i>
Social Media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Newsletter subscribers, YouTube)	Social media: 5000 followers in total by the end of the project	Social Media: >1216	<i>In progress</i>
Networking events and workshops (physical and/or online)	Attend and/or host up to 5 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders, and users.	Attended and hosted more than 20 events 1 joint	<i>Achieved</i>

		H2020 teleconference	
METICOS Newsletters	1 per semester	3	<i>Achieved</i>
Project scientific publications	2-4	3	<i>Achieved</i>
News and blog entries	20	29	<i>In progress</i>
Project video / slideshow	1 initial version to be updated if needed	1 version of the project presentation.	<i>Achieved</i>
Cluster with Relevant Projects & initiatives	Cluster with 5 relevant projects or global initiatives	11 cluster members	<i>Achieved</i>

Table 4 KPIs progress table

6. Exploitation Strategy & METICOS Business Model

6.1 Exploitation strategy

Within this chapter (and in combination with chapter 7 – market analysis), in close liaison with all technical WPs, METICOS maps and sets the ground for the exploitation potential of METICOS outputs/innovations.

Project relevant activities are initiated with the **design of the exploitation strategy**, which will be carried out using the following methodology:

1. A thorough analysis of exploitable foreground per partner and definition of Intellectual Property Rights (licensing approaches, transfer of knowledge to spin-off companies, patents, etc.). Herein, the management of the existing background and the exploitable foreground brought by each partner will take place, following the necessary interaction among partners for having a coherent list of exploitable outcomes.
2. For each exploitable foreground, identification of target stakeholders (relevant product vendors, end-users, etc.) and implementation of dissemination strategy to ensure that all relevant target groups are informed about the appropriate activities & outcomes of the project.
3. Identification of tangible financial plans (i.e. through venture capitals, creation of spin-off, H2020 funding topics, etc.) towards bringing METICOS main results in higher TRL levels and commercialisation.
4. Dedicated business models will be provided for the exploitable outcomes of the project and a business plan for the main exploitable outcome.
5. Targeted workshops organised by METICOS in order to facilitate the exploitation activities of the project, further establishing communication channels with key industrial & targeted stakeholders.

6.2 Overview of METICOS Exploitable Results

This chapter presents the project outcomes, and the joint and individual exploitation plans of the consortium, that paves the way for the METICOS vision to maximise its expected impact. METICOS platform is the main project outcome, and the Business plan will be developed for its future commercialisation by the industrial partners. Overall, METICOS will produce six (6) basic exploitation outcomes including:

- The project platform
- The individual components of the platform
- Services necessary to deploy the platform at the end user sites (replication guidelines, consulting services, installation, training)
- Policy recommendations from the implementation of METICOS platform in replicated real environments
- The results from the pilot cases and

- The scientific knowledge that will be generated through the R&D activities.

Figure 71 METICOS exploitable outcomes

The outcomes will be exploited by the different partner organisations, in IT Industry, Border Control agencies (end users), and Academia. METICOS will develop three basic exploitation options; the business cases for the platform and its components, and concrete exploitation plans to secure the continuation of the scientific knowledge produced, after the end of the project. These exploitation options will be presented to the targeted audience to receive their feedback and engage them in the project activities. Different target audience groups (Industry, Border Control agencies, Research, Related EU funded projects, and Policy makers) will be able to exploit different outcomes.

The main exploitable outcome of the project is the **METICOS platform**. The exploitation and sustainability plan will focus on identifying its sustainability and commercialisation potential. For that reason, the plan for developing the final METICOS business models and business plan will be described and fully available in the final version of the deliverable.

The interoperable and reusable **individual components** of the platform can work and be exploited separately. For these individual components, the exploitation plan will focus on a) exploiting and sustaining the components and the knowledge generated even after the end of the project, and b) identifying which of these components have commercialisation and sustainability potential, thus assisting the technical partners to develop their individual business models.

Strong demonstration and testing (WP10) of the METICOS platform will be divided into two pilot cases: 1. Border Authorities application trials and Pilot#1 Workshop, and 2. Travellers application trials and Pilot#2 Workshop, that will take place in the pilot sites. These demonstrations will produce valuable knowledge, including the **success stories** that will stem from the pilot implementations, the key **policy recommendations** at national and EU level, and the **guidelines** that external Border Control Agencies could follow to deploy the METICOS platform.

Finally, several **scientific papers** with open access will be publicly available, allowing the maximum outreach and exploitation potential of the scientific and technical project knowledge. This action is mostly linked to “Task 11.1 METICOS Communication & dissemination activities, material and publication policy”. The exploitation and sustainability plan will focus on identifying its sustainability and commercialisation potential. The concrete and final plan/progress report for developing the final METICOS business models and business plan will be described in the last iteration of these deliverables, METICOS deliverable report D11.3 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report” expected to be available on project month 36.

6.3 Exploitation Working Group

As described in the D11.1 *Dissemination Communication and Exploitation Plan and Material*, an Exploitation Working Group (EWG) has been assembled, consisting of one representative of each consortium partner (table 5). The EWG will take all the decisions relevant to the implementation of Task 11.2, support the identification, exploitation, and utilisation of the project exploitable outcomes, explore and identify target stakeholders and relevant groups, identify tangible financial plans, develop dedicated financial plans per identified stakeholder, and business models while organising targeted workshops that will also feed to the above-mentioned activities, exploring the possibilities of involving third parties (as consultants or verification factors) to the activities described and expected under the relevant project task. The EWG has online monthly meetings and is expected to collaborate with other Boards established inside the Consortium such as the Security Advisory Board as well as with the Advisory Board, which is expected to provide the EWG with crucial feedback/ verification on the exploitation plans, the financial plans and as well as with the Business Models (per category of stakeholder).

METICOS EXPLOITATION WORKING GROUP MEMBERS		
1	ViLabs	Charalampos Chatzimallis
2	EUC	Christiana Themistocleous
3	ICCS	Gregoris Mentzas (Substitute: Babis Magoutas)
4	NetU	Project Manager
5	NTNU	Sule Yildirim Yayilgan, Erjon Zoto, Mohamed Abomhara, Sarang Shaikh
6	VUB	Franck Dumortier
7	SIMAVI	Monica Florea
8	AIT	Raimund Schatz
9	JOAFG	Georg Aumayr
10	MAGG	Katerina Margariti
11	MoCP/EDPD	Representative
12	PPA	Representative
13	ITPF	Representative
14	SBGS	Representative
15	CY-POL	Representative

Table 5 METICOS Exploitation Working Group

6.4 Joint and Individual exploitation Plans

6.4.1 Joint Exploitation Plan

METICOS partners have initially agreed to jointly commercialise the METICOS Integrating Platform by creating a partnership/ joint venture. The new entity could provide business clients with the overall solution, while some partners will also act as third party big data service providers (e.g., by offering their own services through the METICOS Ecosystem) under specific terms and business framework that will be detailed and agreed upon during the project implementation as part of (a) the business planning and exploitation activities, (b) the SLAs that will govern the relationship of the marketplace administrators and the third-party providers. The role and share of each partner on the joint venture will be determined based on the described foreground and IPR assets identified. On this basis, during the project, METICOS partners will explore joint exploitation alternatives in line with their individual interests and resolve potential conflicts arising from their individual exploitation plans. To finance the commercialisation of the project results and for scaling up, METICOS will consider the use of private and public funds from sources such as the EU investment plan³ and private investors.

6.4.2 Individual exploitation plans

Based on the types of stakeholders in the consortium, different visions for the project exploitation are rising. We can identify three main stakeholder categories:

- Academia and Research (EUC, ICCS, NTNU, VUB, AIT, JPAFG)
- Private companies (NetU, SIMAVI, MAGG, VIL)
- Border control authorities (MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS, CYPOL)

These groups share some exploitation goals, as presented below:

Private Companies	Academia and Research	End Users
METICOS platform as a product, ready to enter the market	Increase the potential to exploit, sustain or even replicate the platform at external Border Control Authorities	Maintain the pilot cases
New individual components that assess the efficiency of no gate solutions in BCP	Improved educational and scientific knowledge based on the policy recommendations and the scientific papers	Innovative policies in the border control domain, at EU and national level
New services (installation, training) for the authorities for the replication of 1. and 2.	Innovative policies in the border control domain, at EU and national level	
Network of organisations in collaboration.	New research collaborations	
New personnel through project participation		
Improvement of skills of the existing personnel		

³ 6 Commission priorities for 2019-2024 (n.d.). European Commission. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024>

Table 6 Exploitation goals per partner type

The final version of the individual exploitation plan of the different partners will be presented in “D11.3 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation final progress report” on M36. The individual exploitation plans are a work in progress since the partners are constantly exploring the opportunities that METICOS offers while the project is running. In order to update the initial individual exploitation plans from D11.1, we distributed the “[Exploitation/innovation questionnaire for technical partners](#)” which is presented in Annex II, in order to have a mapping of the partners’ intentions and goals. The answers to the questionnaire will be analysed by the EWG.

The questionnaire was created using the [EU Survey platform](#), and is structured based on the main necessary information for the understanding of partner’s needs and expectations:

- Questions about the nature of the exploitable result/output
- Questions about how the partner will exploit it
- Questions about the needed support either from the EWG or from a particular partner.

Part of these questions are multiple choice in order to extract the necessary information concretely (e.g. *The exploitable output is 1. Under development, 2. Already developed but not yet being exploited, 3. Being exploited*), and some other are open questions to give the responder the opportunity to explain their goal and proposed actions (e.g. *Briefly mention the exploitation activities you are planning to implement or you have already implemented within the project duration*).

Apart from the development of the individual exploitation plans, this questionnaire will provide useful input, to help the EWG to structure the final joint exploitation plan efficiently and give the partners the most suitable roles.

Figure 72 Innovation Questionnaire

6.5 METICOS platform – Business Model Canvas

METICOS main exploitable output is the METICOS platform to integrate information systems and networks of sensors to validate the efficiency and users’ acceptance of Smart Border technologies. This platform will process information from different sources into a multiscale approach for integrating information from border authorities’ information systems and Smart Borders sensors to technology acceptance models and social sentiment monitoring. METICOS platform will be a valuable tool for border management for more efficient, fast, and effective next-generation Smart Borders. The platform will evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of smart borders technologies, the travellers’ satisfaction and acceptability on the use of these technologies, and iii) The level of future-proofing is improved with the ability to add new data sources as threats evolve. The platform architecture (figure 73) has the capability to concentrate and handle the data of many devices or services, thus covering a wide range of use case scenarios.

Figure 73 METICOS platform architecture

The consortium has already created an initial Business Model about the METICOS platform that will be subject to reviews and iterations as the exploitation activities move forward (in parallel with the project activities and progress). Dedicated Business Models will also be developed per individual component with a strong focus on the different customer segments and will be available in project deliverable report 11.3. At this point, the consortium has concentrated on the METICOS platform.

For the METICOS platform the consortium has followed the Business Model Canvas⁴ methodology. It allows to describe, design, visualise, challenge, invent and pivot business models and it was selected because of its broad popularity and its simple form. The initial BMC about the METICOS platform is displayed below:

Figure 74 Business Model Canvas

The building blocks of the BMC include the *customer segments*, the *value propositions*, the *customer relationships*, the needed *recourses*, the *key activities* and *partners*, the *channels* of dissemination, the *cost structure*, and the *revenue streams*.

The presentation of the building blocks is customer oriented. The customers are divided into two subcategories: 1) EU agencies and national governments, and 2) IT companies. The colours represent the elements in the canvas that refer to the different customers:

1. Blue: Elements referring to the EU agencies and national governments
2. Yellow: Elements referring to the private companies
3. Green: Elements referring to both categories

Customer segments

The building block of customer segments includes all the potential customers of the METICOS platform, willing to pay for the product. The customers are the identified target groups to whom the METICOS platform intends to offer its value proposition. The goal of the consortium is to map the needs of the target audience and exceed their expectations. Based on the initial scope of the project and the research conducted in the context of the exploitation planning, there are three customer groups identified:

- EU agencies
- National Governments

⁴ <https://strategyzer.com/canvas>

- IT companies.

EU agencies: The EU agencies like FRONTEX and EU-Lisa are the primer potential customer of the METICOS platform, that are interested in the monitoring and evaluation of the border control technologies they use, and how they are perceived by the passengers. This knowledge can guide them in adopting more acceptable and “friendly” practices, maximising both the passengers’ satisfaction and security.

National governments: The national governments are also a vital customer of the METICOS platform. The EU member states do not have a uniform system in terms of border control technologies and they can benefit from the METICOS platform, in order to evaluate their existing tools and decide what kind of additional technologies they can adopt, considering passengers’ perspective.

IT companies: Private companies that work in IT and security can be potential customers of the METICOS platform in case they want to acquire the technology for further exploitation. This customer segment is secondary, but the exploitation working group will explore this potential, especially after drafting the individual exploitation plans.

Value proposition

The value proposition of the METICOS applies to the needs of the three customer segments that are presented above. These needs include:

- Evaluation and assessment of existing border control tools
- Optimisation of the tools’ effectiveness
- Cost Reduction
- Risk Reduction.

Evaluation and assessment of existing border control tools: The METICOS solution is a sustainable and coherent ecosystem that accommodates for the local, regional and cross-border differences from an EU wide perspective, based on a comprehensive framework of underlying social, cultural, ethical and legal principles. It identifies, evaluates and assesses whether the current border control technologies respect and promote human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, privacy, the rule of law and protection of fundamental rights, including the right to privacy and data protection, good governance and security.

Optimisation of the tools’ effectiveness: After the assessment, the results will help the agencies map the issues and gaps of the existing technologies and optimise their practices towards security and acceptance.

Cost reduction: Due to the assessment of the tools, the agencies will know which technologies are more acceptable and secure, and the unsuccessful trials of new tools will be minimised, reducing the cost.

Risk reduction: In continuation of the cost reduction, fewer unsuccessful trials means fewer possibilities to expose the LEAs, the operators, and the passengers to security risks.

Customer relationships

Customer relationships are the links a company establishes between itself and its different customer segments. They describe the types of relationships that the company has with the specific customer

segments. METICOS targets EU agencies and national governments. Therefore, the consortium focuses from its very beginning on a customer retention policy, by setting up the following types of customer relationships:

- Long term
- Personal

Long-term: METICOS will interact with the customers on a recurring basis through the already established communication channels (online and offline), and the customer support services.

Personal: The consortium members will be personally involved and will support the customers according to their expertise.

Key recourses

Key resources are the most important assets to make the business model happen. Without them it is impossible to create and deliver the value proposition. METICOS will need the following key resources:

- IT/Data infrastructure
- Personnel
- Financial resources.

IT/Data infrastructure: METICOS will need company facilities in which most tasks will be executed. The physical key resources include servers and the hosting environment and internet infrastructure for the servers and the storage.

Personnel: The METICOS platform will need human resources for research, development, support and marketing purposes in order to operate.

Financial recourses: In order to cover the costs of the METICOS platform, additional funding will be needed after the completion of the project. The exploitation working group will map the potential additional funding sources from private investors or additional European funds

Key activities

In order to execute the business model, some key activities have to take place.

- Further development, integration and maintenance
- Marketing and sales
- Customer service

Further development, integration, and maintenance: These activities aim at maintaining and updating the platform and extending its functionalities. The maintenance of the platform includes bug fixing. These bugs are reported by customers through the customer service department.

Marketing and sales: These activities will secure existing partnerships and will find new customers.

Customer service: These activities should ensure the proper operation of the METICOS platform for all customers.

Key partners

The key partners are the network of suppliers and partners that make the business model work. Key partners for running the METICOS business model include:

- METICOS consortium
- EU agencies
- National governments
- LEAs
- IT companies.

METICOS consortium: This mainly refers to the developers of the components and the business experts willing to take up the results.

EU agencies: As a primary customer segment, the EU agencies are also a key partner that not only can leverage from the METICOS business model but can also provide feedback for further optimisation.

National governments: Like the EU agencies, the national governments are both an important customer segment, and a source for feedback.

LEAs: The LEAs are the end users of the METICOS platform. They will have the hands on experience of the product. As partners, they can contribute to the design and optimisation of the METICOS platform. In this vein, LEAs already participate in the METICOS consortium to test the technology and provide their input.

IT companies: These companies can leverage the METICOS business model, either as customers, or collaborators to further develop and exploit the platform.

Channels

Channels are used to get the product/service from the firm to the customer. METICOS communicates with and reaches the customers to deliver the value proposition in the following ways:

- Online channels
- Offline activities

Online channels: METICOS will maintain its website and social media for communication purposes. More attention will be given to the website, since the customers are mostly agencies and public authorities. The online channels will be more useful for approaching private companies.

Offline activities: METICOS will organise training sessions, workshops and pitch events for the customers to disseminate the news about the METICOS platform and demonstrate how it operates. This communication channel applies for all customer segments.

Cost structure

The cost structure describes all costs incurred to operate the business model. The cost structure is highly related to three pre-defined blocks of the business model, key activities and key resources. The operating costs of METICOS business model are the following:

- Development, integration, and maintenance costs
- Marketing costs
- Training costs
- Infrastructure costs

Development, integration, and maintenance costs: As already mentioned earlier, these costs will cover the key activities of development, integration and maintenance of the METICOS platform.

Marketing costs: The marketing costs will cover the key activity “marketing and sales”

Training costs: The training costs are both part of the key activities and the offline activities in the dissemination channels.

Infrastructure costs: The infrastructure costs will cover the IT/Data infrastructure from the key resources.

Revenue streams

Revenue streams are the methods by which money comes into a company. The revenue streams that METICOS will explore are the following:

- Direct sales (one-time payment)
- Licensing fees (scalability)
- Maintenance and support fees
- Training and consulting fees.

Direct sales (one-time payment): The METICOS consortium can sell the METICOS platform directly to the agencies and governments and get an onetime payment from them as a purchase.

Licensing fees (scalability): The METICOS consortium can sell the licence of the METICOS Platform to another IT company that will then sell the product to the agencies and governments that are interested. This payment is scalable, and the license has an expiration date that has to be renewed and repaid if the company wishes to continue having the right to sell the METICOS platform.

Maintenance and support fees: The METICOS consortium can provide maintenance and support services according to their expertise, either directly to the end users, or the IT companies.

Training and consulting fees: The METICOS consortium can provide training and consulting services according to their expertise, either directly to the end users, or the IT companies.

In this section we presented a first version of the METICOS Business model, using the Business Model Canvas methodology. The final version will be outlined in in “D11.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report” on M36.

6.6 METICOS commercialisation potential – SWOT analysis

An initial commercialisation plan for the METICOS solution has been conducted using SWOT analysis. A SWOT Analysis is a very effective tool to assess the current position of a project, before implementing any new strategies, including a firm assessment of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats to deal with. By conducting a SWOT analysis, this section analyses the advantages and disadvantages of applying a plan for enhancing the border control management in the EU region, as well as the opportunities and challenges that might be faced during the implementation of an exploitation and sustainability plan from the consortium.

<p style="text-align: center;">STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unified tactical picture of the border • State-of-the-art technologies (sensors and radars) • Safety (minimum crew required + access to dangerous areas) • Tailored made according to the customer’s needs • User friendly • Avoid overcrowding 	<p style="text-align: center;">WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some technologies are not fully ready yet • The components of the METICOS platform are developed by different partners / different IPRs involved • Lack of standardization • Lack of capital requirement for infrastructure projects • Immigrants and Refugees’ control
<p style="text-align: center;">OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart border control technology market is expected to grow • Coverage of air/ground/water and adaptability to adverse conditions • Single Free Market and free circulation of people gives the opportunity for implementing such technologies 	<p style="text-align: center;">THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different in-existent MS individual laws • Technical safety/ cyber threat • Future demand for cheaper systems or components

Figure 75 SWOT analysis

Starting with the strengths of the METICOS solution, these include the unified tactical picture of the borders, the state of the art technologies that can be assessed, the safety due to the minimum crew needs, the adaptability to the customer’s needs, the user friendly environment and the faster service of the passengers which will lead to less crowded borders.

The weaknesses of the METICOS solutions are the unreadiness of some technologies that are included in the METICOS solution, the fact that different partners of the consortium are building different components of the METICOS solution, which leads to different IPRs, the lack of standardisation (at the moment), the lack of capital requirement for infrastructure projects (at the moment), and the challenge of immigrant and refugee control during the pilots.

On the other hand, the METICOS solution leverages from the opportunity of entering the market of smart border control technologies which is expected to grow. Due to its adaptable nature, it covers air, ground and water transportation. Last, the single free market and free movement of people give the opportunity for implementing such technologies.

Lastly, the threats for the METICOS solution are the different laws applied in the different member states, the issues of technical safety and cyber threats, and the future demand for cheaper systems or components.

This is a preliminary version of the SWOT analysis. In the final deliverable with the completed market analysis, a final SWOT table will be presented. The EWG is constantly working on this, and the foreseen Exploitation workshops will have a significant contribution to the final version of the SWOT analysis.

6.7 Upcoming Exploitation Steps

In order to achieve the exploitation goals, METICOS will structure a road map with the next steps of the project towards the final exploitation and sustainability strategy. The final strategy will be codesigned and validated with the rest of the consortium. The following actions will take place:

METICOS upcoming exploitation activities and steps
A series of exploitation workshops, as provisioned in T11.2, to gather all the information and produce the final exploitation and sustainability strategy of the METICOS exploitable results. The consortium will produce the METICOS business models, SWOT analysis and IPR plans per exploitable result.
An updated and targeted market analysis of each exploitable result.
Webinars targeted to technical and scientific partners to build a business case.
Webinar targeted the end-users where the exploitation objectives are presented together with a plan on how to achieve them.
Pilot partners to present the pilot demonstrations and their impact on the travellers and the border control staff.
Organisation of a mini workshop to communicate the METICOS business models with external experts.
Distribution to all partners a final exploitation questionnaire.
Development of replication guidelines.
Identification of key policy recommendations and best practices.
Dissemination and exploitation of the policy recommendations.

Table 7 METICOS upcoming exploitation activities and steps

6.8 Innovation management

The METICOS project will follow an innovation management approach, in line with the **Innovation Radar Methodology**⁵, to identify high potential innovations of the METICOS project. The activities will be carried out in the context of WP11.

“Innovation Radar aims to identify high-potential innovations and innovators. It is an important source of actionable intelligence on innovations emerging from research and innovation projects funded through European Union programmes.” ([European Commission](#)).

This methodology has two indicators, the *Innovation Potential Indicator* for measuring innovation development towards commercialisation, and the *Innovator Capacity Indicator* for capturing the innovative capacity of the innovators behind these innovations. The first indicator refers to the innovation readiness, the innovation management and the market potential. The second indicator refers to the innovator’s ability to commercialise the product, and the innovator’s environment. ([Booklet Innovation Radar](#))

An initial innovation strategy has been drafted, constituted of four (4) basic steps:

1. Mapping of the innovation aspects of METICOS
2. Assessment framework
3. Coordination of Innovation management
4. Exploitation and Sustainability

Figure 76 below presents the sub sections of each step:

⁵ Innovation Radar methodology (n.d.). European Commission. Retrieved from <https://www.innoradar.eu/methodology>

Figure 76 METICOS initial Innovation management strategy

The innovation strategy is still under construction. The fully developed steps and actions will be described in the final deliverable 11.3.

6.9 Intellectual Property Rights

In case of exploitation, either from individual partners or from the whole METICOS consortium, Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) should be handled carefully. The IPR strategy and the exploitation management are handled in the Consortium Agreement and the T2.3. More precisely, the Consortium Agreement defines the rules to apply for the management of IPR, especially regarding patents, exploitation of common foreground generated by the project. Additionally, T2.3 deals with knowledge management and the potential revision of the Consortium Agreement especially regarding: Ownership of the knowledge, Protection of knowledge, Publication of results, Use and dissemination of knowledge arising from the project, access rights, incompatible or restrictive commitments, use of marks, etc.

IPRs are a particularly important aspect that the METICOS consortium needs to clarify within the context of the exploitation strategy, since they define, for the most part, obligations regarding who should engage them in the exploitation plans and how to implement them. It is essential to clarify which one(s) of the partners will hold the IPRs of the project outcomes after the project's duration, since that partner(s) will be responsible to ensure that the exploitation strategy is being followed.

7. METICOS initial Market analysis

In recent years, “No-gate solution” tools have opened a pan-European dialogue regarding smart border control technologies and travelers’ acceptability. Although the dilemma about the modification and update of the legal framework is prevalent, arguments in favour of the modernisation of the border control practices are based on the efficiency, better safety, and free movement of products and people. The arguments against the “no gate solutions” are based on the security dilemma about state sovereignty.

METICOS can answer this dilemma, through the METICOS solution, providing the border control agencies and the European Union with insights about the efficiency and travelers’ acceptability of such practices. This chapter is the first step in understanding the possibilities and opportunities for METICOS’ long-term sustainability, exploitation and commercialisation’s prospects. The market analysis contributes to identifying the end-users and potential customers, testing the concept and the perceived added value, developing new strategies, solving potential challenges, overcoming barriers, and discovering new business opportunities. The full market analysis to help the consortium develop the final exploitation and sustainability plans of METICOS will be presented in M36.

7.1 Overview

Market analysis, is an effective tool contributing to the success of a product or service, providing an in-depth mapping, and understanding of the market trends, the legal framework, the existing competition, as well as the potential customers and their exact needs. Usually, a market analysis consists of characterisation and determination of market actors (service providers, manufacturers, etc.), competition and trends, analysis of regulations associated with the sector/product, analysis of the main drivers for demand of the product, service to customer (quality, price, specific technical knowledge, innovation, credentials, etc.) and the analysis of the potential market (volume, growth trends etc.).⁶

7.1.1 Market Actors

The market actors are the stakeholders that affect the market in a specific sector. In the case of METICOS, four types of market actors have been identified: 1. end users, 2. customers, 3. competitors, and 4. partners.

Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs), like the police and the border control agencies, are the target **end users** of the METICOS solution. Also, in the category of end users, the facility managers, the system operators, and the travellers are included. On the other hand, potential **customers** are the national governments, and the EU agencies responsible for border security (e.g. Frontex or Europol) that will buy the solution to accoutre the end users. In addition, private companies working on technology and security are considered potential customers. This market has some special characteristics, since the information about the practices and tools used by the abovementioned end users, is usually sensitive and even confidential. The actors defined as customers and the LEAs as end users, are also potential

⁶ Market Analysis Provides Key Components of Business Plan (n.d.). Investment Bank. Retrieved from <https://investmentbank.com/market-analysis-provides-key-components-of-business-plan/>

and actual **partners**, which automatically leads to the adoption of the technology by most of the partners, facilitating the commercialisation of the METICOS solution.

The competition in the sector is another market player that the METICOS consortium has to take into account. As **competitors** are defined, other EU funded projects working on border control technologies, offering a similar solution, and tech companies and manufacturers. In this deliverable, an initial list of the competitors has been drafted.

Overall, many of the market actors can apply in more than one category. To better understand the METICOS market actors, the figure below visualises the correlations and overlapping among the actors.

Figure 77 Market Actors interconnections

7.1.2 Market size

The Schengen area is a space with no internal borders, along with the application of European policies regarding the external borders, the common rules on border control and the EU visa, in cooperation with the police. The ISF (Internal Security Fund) of the EU for border and visa strand is 2.76 billion euro. Also, 25% of the EU’s Multiannual Financial Framework is dedicated to ISF Borders and Visa. On top of that, the EU has allocated another 9.26 euros from the home affairs budget to asylum, migration and other financings, for the relevant EU agencies, like Frontex. Additionally, the Union has allocated 0.55 billion euros for borders via Customs 2020 programme, and 1.7 billion for improving border security via the H2020 framework programme for research and innovation.

The European border security market is expected to grow from 9.502,93 million € in 2021 to 15.598,53 million € by 2028. Also, it is estimated to grow at a CAGR of 6% by 2027⁷. Most of the funding in this sector in Europe comes from France, Italy, Spain, and UK⁸. Illegal activities like terrorism and human

⁷ Europe Border Security Market – Growth, trends, COVID-19 Impact and forecasts (2022-2027). Mordor Intelligence. Retrieved from: <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/europe-border-security-market>

⁸ Border Security Market Research Report: By Platform (Ground, Aerial, Naval), System (Laser, Radar, Camera, Wide Band Wireless Communication, Perimeter Intrusion, Unmanned Vehicles, C2C, Biometric Systems and others) and Region (North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, Middle East & Africa and Latin America) - Forecast till 2027. Market Research Future. Retrieved from <https://www.marketresearchfuture.com/reports/border-security-market-1662>

trafficking increased the interest for innovative security systems as a countermeasure. Border security systems function as first line defense against such threads, blocking the illegal movement of people and goods. In a more advanced stage, security practices can integrate proper screening systems at specific checkpoints. The market is growing, giving the opportunity for deploying and developing new border security systems, during the forecast period⁹.

Another related market is the global managed services market¹⁰, concerning the outsourcing of certain computing and IT related processes such as cloud computing, IT infrastructure, and managed IT security. It is expected to grow and reach 494 billion euros by 2028 while exhibiting a CAGR of 12.6% between 2021 to 2028. The extensive demand in IT, healthcare, financial and telecommunication, drives this global market, with Businesses adopting these services to upgrade and innovate their infrastructure¹¹. In this context the potential customers of METICOS could outsource the operating services to the METICOS partners.

Also, the global market of information security products and services¹² is forecast to reach almost 155.2 billion by 2024. Information security is the practice of managing access to information, whether that is securing information from unauthorised access, or verifying the identity of those who claim to have authority to access information. These products and services include assessment platforms like the one that METICOS is developing, and hence, the project constitutes part of this market. Plus, according to Statista study, the size of the global video surveillance market¹³ in 2023 is going to reach 55.55 billion euros, in comparison to 26.7 billion in 2017. Due to the migration crisis, the EU and the member states are investing more in border control technologies, to secure their borders¹⁴. As the security market grows and becomes more technology oriented, there is a need for assessment tools to ensure the social acceptance of the border control technologies. This need leads to more market opportunities for the METICOS solution.

Finally, the global cyber security market size is anticipated to reach 298 billion euros by 2028, showing a CAGR of 12.0% during the forecast period. Overall, the rising number of e-commerce platforms and the integration of machine learning, internet-of-things (IoT), and cloud are expected to boost the market's growth.¹⁵ According to the European Cybersecurity Organisation report, the member states

⁹ Europe Border Security Market – Growth, trends, COVID-19 Impact and forecasts (2022-2027). Mordor Intelligence. Retrieved from: <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/europe-border-security-market>

¹⁰ Managed Services Market to Hit USD 557.1 Billion by 2028; Increasing Adoption of Cloud-based Managed Security to Augment Market Growth: Future Business Infights (2021). Globe Newswire by notified. Retrieved from: <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2021/09/28/2304304/0/en/Managed-Services-Market-to-Hit-USD-557-10-Billion-by-2028-Increasing-Adoption-of-Cloud-based-Managed-Security-to-Augment-Market-Growth-Fortune-Business-Insights.html>

¹¹ Forecast size of the managed services market worldwide from 2020-2026 (2022). Statista. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/590884/worldwide-managed-services-market-size/>

¹² Size of the information security technology market from 2016 to 2024 (2022). Statista. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/640141/worldwide-information-security-market-size/#statisticContainer>

¹³ Size of the global video surveillance market between 2016 and 2025 (2020). Statista. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/864838/video-surveillance-market-size-worldwide/>

¹⁴ Smart borders, Immigration Enforcement & Border Security Markets in Europe – 2017-2022 (2017). HSRC. Retrieved from <https://homelandsecurityresearch.com/reports/smart-borders-immigration-enforcement-border-security-markets-focus-europe/>

¹⁵ Cyber security market size, share & COVID-19 impact analysis, by component (solution and services), by deployment type (Cloud and on-premise), by Enterprise size (Small & Medium Enterprise and Large Enterprise), By Industry (BFSI, IT and Telecommunications, Retail, Healthcare, Government, manufacturing, Travel and Transportation, Energy and Utilities and others) and Region Forecast, 2021-2028 (n.d.). Fortune Business insights. Retrieved from <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/industry-reports/cyber-security-market-101165>

invest in internet and network security projects for defence and research to guard their confidential data and information.¹⁶

To conclude, different markets are fertile for security products and services like the METICOS solution, which boosts the chances for success in the marketplace. However, the exact expenditure statistics are not available on the national level. This market analysis is at an initial stage. A more specific market analysis will be conducted in the final version, dedicated to each METICOS exploitable result.

7.1.3 Key Players for METICOS

In the sector of border control, there are several key players, mostly European bodies and agencies, that could be potential high-level partners of the METICOS solution. The participation of these players could massively facilitate the commercialisation process.

7.1.3.1 The European Commission

The European Commission is responsible for proposing and implementing the EU legislation, including the border control legislation. Given that, it is the most valuable player. The EC is committed to provide high level protection to the European citizens in the civil aviation field, by adopting and ensuring common safety rules and by measures. The legal framework set by the EC, is more than relevant to the METICOS project, impacting its outcomes.

7.1.3.2 EU agencies

EU-Lisa: The European Union Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale IT Systems in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (eu-LISA), provides a long-term solution for the operational management of large-scale IT systems, which are essential instruments in the implementation of the asylum, border management and migration policies of the EU. The Agency currently manages Eurodac, the second generation Schengen Information System (SIS II) and the Visa Information System (VIS). Further to these, EU-LISA is developing the Entry/Exit System (EES), the European Travel Information Authorisation System (ETIAS), and the European Criminal Records Information System - Third-Country Nationals (ECRIS-TCN). These systems and the pre-existing ones are being built/adapted to ensure Interoperability - improved access to information stored in EU information systems and identity management at an EU level.

EASA: The European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) is the central European strategy for aviation safety. The agency promotes the highest common standards in terms of safety and environmental protection in civil aviation. The Agency develops, implements, and monitors the regulations in the Member States, while it also supports them in terms of technical expertise, training, and research. The national authorities are also in cooperation with the agency. The role of the agency as a regulator on border control, constitutes is a partner of great interest for the METICOS project.

Europol: Europol is the official European Union's law enforcement agency. The agency works for the safety of the European citizens and work along with the Member states to combat terrorism,

¹⁶ Cyber Security Market to Reach USD 366.1 Billion by 2028; Surging Number of E-Commerce Platforms to Amplify Market Growth: Says Future Business Insights (2022). Global Newswire. Retrieved from <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2022/01/05/2361317/0/en/Cyber-Security-Market-to-Reach-USD-366-10-Billion-by-2028-Surging-Number-of-E-Commerce-Platforms-to-Amplify-Market-Growth-Says-Fortune-Business-Insights.html>

cybercrime etc. The agency also has close ties with many non-EU countries and organisations. Europol and METICOS share an interest in advanced border control practices. Also, both can contribute in terms of expertise and equipment. This common interest constitutes Europol a valuable partner for METICOS.

Eurocontrol: Eurocontrol is an intergovernmental organisation committed to support European aviation by delivering technical excellence and civil-military expertise across the full spectrum of air traffic management. The agency can be a valuable partner for the METICOS project since it could facilitate the technology integration into the regulated airspace.

FRONTEX: In 2004, the European Agency for the Management of Operational Cooperation at the External Borders of the Member States of the European Union (FRONTEX) was established. Its mission is to improve the integrated management of external borders, (land-sea) ports, airports of the Member States and of the Member States of the European Union, to which the provisions of Community law on the crossing of external borders apply. Although Member States have the responsibility for controlling and supervising the external borders, the Agency facilitates and strengthens the implementation of the measures provided at EU level related to border management.

Frontex could be a useful METICOS partner, on the basis of information exchange and joint operations to research and innovation. METICOS could have a massive contribution to Frontex activities and FRONTEX could provide technical support and expertise. Complementary, the **EUROSUR** (European Border Surveillance system) is a framework for information exchange and cooperation between Member States and Frontex to raise situational awareness and increase reaction capability at the external borders. This framework can facilitate the flow of information and further support of the METICOS solution, in a potential cooperation with FRONTEX.

7.1.4 EU Regulations

Each EU member state has developed their national border control policies to address current and future security challenges. Although, the European legal framework gives some direction, in terms of the national regulations on border control. The respective European regulations that the METICOS project should take into account, are presented below.

7.1.4.1 *The Schengen Acquis and the Schengen Borders Code*

Schengen Borders Code¹⁷ of the European Parliament and the Council of 9 March 2016: It mandated how border checks were to be carried out, under which circumstances border checks may be relaxed, how border crossing points are to be architecturally designed, how border surveillance is to be carried out, and under which circumstances entry may be refused. Furthermore, the Schengen Borders Code details the abolition of controls at internal borders, as well as the criteria for their resumption or reintroduction.

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2016/399. Retrieved from
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0399>

7.1.4.2 European Commission actions

The Commission, as a significant regulatory body has taken actions on border management. The most important actions are presented below.

Regulation (EC) No 216/2008¹⁸

This regulation sets the main rules and principles for a unified framework civil aviation safety in Europe, including the creation, aim, and structure of the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). Every aeronautical product, as well as the personnel and involved organisations, need to abide to this regulation.

European Border and Coast Guard and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1052/2013 and (EU) 2016/1624 (Regulation 2019/1986)¹⁹

Aiming to develop and implement European integrated border management at national and Union level, which is a necessary corollary to the free movement of persons within the Union and is a fundamental component of an area of freedom, security and justice.

Large-scale information systems are the more generic term used in the European Union for the different Union-wide databases that have been established over the previous decades. Notably, most of these database systems are connected to border or migration control.

Regulation (EC) No 1987/2006: Establishment, Operation and Use of the Second-Generation Schengen Information System (SIS II)²⁰

The Schengen Information System ('SIS') set up pursuant to the provisions of Title IV of the Convention of 19 June 1990 implementing the Schengen Agreement of 14 June 1985 between the governments of the States of the Benelux Economic Union, the Federal Republic of Germany and the French Republic on the gradual abolition of checks at their common borders (the 'Schengen Convention'), and its development, SIS 1+, constitute an essential tool for the application of the provisions of the Schengen acquis as integrated into the framework of the European Union. The development of the second generation of SIS ('SIS II') by the Commission replaced SIS as created pursuant to the Schengen Convention.

Regulation (EU) 2017/2226 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2017²¹

The Entry-Exit System was established by Regulation (EU). It establishes an Entry/Exit System (EES) to Register Entry and Exit Data and Refusal of Entry Data of Third-Country Nationals Crossing the External Borders of the Member States and Determining the Conditions for Access to the EES for Law Enforcement Purposes.

¹⁸ Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council (2008). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32008R0216>

¹⁹ European Border and Coast Guard and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1052/2013 and (EU) 2016/1624 (Regulation 2019/1986). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R1896>

²⁰ Regulation (EC) No 1987/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 on the Establishment, Operation and Use of the Second Generation Schengen Information System (SIS II). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32006R1987>

²¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/2226 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2017. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/LSU/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R2226>

7.1.5 Other providers

In the context of this market analysis, an initial mapping of other providers in the sector of border control technologies is presented in 7.1.6. The potential competition for the METICOS solution includes other EU funded projects under the same call, as well as private tech companies in the security and defense industry.

7.1.5.1 EU funded projects

These projects suggest similar solutions and can be seen as potential competitors in the sector of border control technology assessment.

[PERSONA](#) structures a unified and tailored Impact Assessment Method for No-Gate Crossing Point Solutions capable of appropriately evaluating border controlling technologies and of ensuring that these solutions meet the requirements and expectations of governments, LEAS, and border crossing individuals. The PERSONA Community of Stakeholders comprises members from three different key groups:

- Border Administration and Law Enforcement Agencies
- Security companies, standard and regulatory organizations, policy makers
- Think tanks, Civil society Organisations and NGOs

The goal of this community is to gather independent experts from relevant disciplines who advise and give feedback on the development of the project's impact assessment method.

[D4FLY](#) is a research and innovation project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme "Secure societies – Protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens". The project focuses on enhancing the quality and efficiency of identity verification at border crossings in all modalities: land, air, and sea by providing faster and more secure border control solutions.

The project identifies existing or possible future fraud methods in regard to travel documents and identity, creates new technologies in automated document fraud, face morphing and impostor attack detection to overcome the limitations of current document readers and corresponding software in automated and non-automated border control scenarios, and enables new technologies in unobtrusive person identification that improve the recognition of travellers on-the-move as well as known suspects giving special focus on applicability to the given infrastructure. Also, it produces evidence-based knowledge on document fraud and biometrics on the fly in compliance with European societal values, fundamental rights and applicable legislation, supported by end-users, inspired by privacy- and security by design. Finally, the project will provide a cost-benefit analysis and plan for the take up of the project results after the completion of the project, having first established the legal and social propriety of such initiatives.

[CRITERIA](#) project seeks to strengthen and expand existing risk analysis methods, by introducing novel approaches, such as identifying risk factors from qualitative evidence (e.g. narrative analysis), building composite indicators (e.g. using sentiment indicators to predict behaviour), incorporating risk interaction and risk cascading assessments and consolidating the human security and human rights dimensions of border security. Building upon existing text, media, data and network analysis technology, CRITERIA develops and evaluates advanced analysis technologies and tools that are

tailored to the new comprehensive risk and vulnerability indicators of the CRiTERIA methodology. They focus on the role of narratives, events, attitudes, perception of situations for migration-related decisions as well as for the evolution of migration-related situations, the vulnerability of borders and humans and the development of threats.

[ITFLOWS](#) generates novel insights on migration, providing accurate predictions and adequate management solutions of migration flows in the European Union in the phases of reception, relocation, settlement, and integration of migration, according to a wide range of human factors and using multiple sources of information. These insights will be provided by an evidence-based ICT enabled solution (the EUMigraTool) and precise models. All solutions will have fitness for purpose continually validated by policymakers and practitioners in cooperation with civil-society organisations in a dynamic and iterative process. The EUMigraTool includes analysis of media content from TV-news (video content), web-news and social media (text content) using deep learning and proposing novel deep architectures in generative modelling and forecasting using sequential data. Predictions incorporate algorithms that consider the two key challenges associated with prediction of migration: (a) Adequate selection of relevant data sources, and (b) correct selection of the potential drivers to be monitored and to the warning thresholds to be set.

7.1.5.2 Private sector

The companies presented below are considered as entities that could potentially “compete” METICOS in the industry. The entities and information below have derived from online public information that is available on the web and have been identified during the literature review that took place for the development of METICOS market analysis.²²

[Thales Group](#): Multinational group, designs and builds electrical systems and provides services for the aerospace, space, defence, transportation and security markets.

THALES is active in the sector of Digital Identity and Security and delivers identity and biometric solutions to governments, public authorities and private entities in the fields of civil identity and public security. In addition to electronic travel documents and national e-ID cards, Thales offers border agencies, government authorities and airports a complete portfolio of solutions that help secure, automate and facilitate border and passenger management for air, land or sea operations. The solution delivers seamless travel with online visa applications with Thales Gemalto Visa Management, improves border intelligence for detection and prevention with Thales Gemalto Border Management and Automated Border Identification System, and offers convenience for travellers for fast and secure border crossing with Thales Gemalto ABC Gate and Border Kiosk.

[Indra Sistemas SA](#): Global provider of solutions in specific segments of the Transport and Defence markets, leader in developing end-to-end technology solutions in the Defence and Security field and many others.

The company provides customised solutions in terms of border security, according to the special needs of each country. Their flexible and integrated solutions cover all kinds of borders (land, sea, river and

²² The following entities have been included as examples. METICOS has no intention of advertising or sharing any kind of information, positive or negative, about any third party. There is also no intention to compare or compete with the aforementioned entities. This section is simply a part of a “typical” market analysis structure and nothing further.

offshore platforms), adapted to client needs and system requirements. The company has a wide experience in integrating and reusing existing systems, using proprietary technology like MRI surveillance aircraft, radars, iSense buried sensors, etc. They maintain close relationships with the leading sensor manufacturers and they take leadership in R&D programs including Perseus, Seahorse, and Seabilla.

In the context of these customised solutions, they can provide the customer with assessment tools that can evaluate the impact of the border control technologies they use.

Leidos: Global provider of Modernising infrastructure, systems, and security for government agencies and commercial markets.

Leidos is active in the sector of Biometrics and identity technologies, delivering large-scale systems integration, design and development of biometric solutions and technical evaluations, taking into account, the critical parameter of the safety of citizens and security of nations. Also, they provide Security Detection and Automation solutions for the airports, respecting travellers' needs.

In this regard, the company can develop solutions that take under consideration the social impact of the proposed solutions.

Overall, METICOS shares common characteristics with its competitors in the sector of border control technology assessment. However, the Exploitation Working Group is working on structuring an exploitation and sustainability plan, that will demonstrate why METICOS provides the most efficient solution.

8. Regulatory and standardisation reporting

The involved partners continuously follow/list 1) regulations and 2) standards in the general field of privacy/security-enhancing tools for no gate solutions, including BCP technologies, travel documents, biometrics and mobile devices.

The aim of this step is not yet to start analysing the regulations and standards applicable to the general field of interest but only to list these and briefly explain their purpose. Based on this list, we already have a general overview of the regulatory and standardisation landscape to decide on what to focus on a next step.

In the context of T11.4 Analysis of the Regulatory and Standardisation European Landscape on secure technologies for no gate solution in BCPs, the respective regulations and standards were currently listed:

1. Regulations (and other policy papers) applicable to:

- Border control checks:
 - Regulation (EU) 2016/399 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on a Union Code on the rules governing the movement of persons across borders (Schengen Borders Code), as consolidated on 11/06/2019
 - Regulation (EC) No 810/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a Community Code on Visas (Visa Code)
 - Regulation (EU) 2018/1806 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 listing the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement
 - Regulation (EU) 2018/1240 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 September 2018 establishing a European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS) and amending Regulations (EU) No 1077/2011, (EU) No 515/2014, (EU) 2016/399, (EU) 2016/1624 and (EU) 2017/2226, as consolidated on 03/08/2021.
 - Council Directive 2004/82/EC of 29 April 2004 on the obligation of carriers to communicate passenger data.
 - Directive (EU) 2016/681 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the use of passenger name record (PNR) data for the prevention, detection, investigation and prosecution of terrorist offences and serious crime
- Large-scale IT systems in the area of Border control (and the processing of biometrics therein)
 - Regulation (EC) No 1987/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 on the establishment, operation and use of the second generation Schengen Information System (SIS II), as consolidated on 28/12/2020
 - Regulation (EC) No 767/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 July 2008 concerning the Visa Information System (VIS) and the exchange of data between Member States on short-stay visas (VIS Regulation), as consolidated on 03/08/2021

- Regulation (EU) 2017/2226 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2017 establishing an Entry/Exit System (EES) to register entry and exit data and refusal of entry data of third-country nationals crossing the external borders of the Member States and determining the conditions for access to the EES for law enforcement purposes, and amending the Convention implementing the Schengen Agreement and Regulations (EC) No 767/2008 and (EU) No 1077/2011, as consolidated on 03/08/2021
- Regulation (EU) No 603/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on the establishment of 'Eurodac' for the comparison of fingerprints for the effective application of Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the Member State responsible for examining an application for international protection lodged in one of the Member States by a third-country national or a stateless person and on requests for the comparison with Eurodac data by Member States' law enforcement authorities and Europol for law enforcement purposes, and amending Regulation (EU) No 1077/2011 establishing a European Agency for the operational management of large-scale IT systems in the area of freedom, security and justice
- Regulation (EU) 2019/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2019 on establishing a framework for interoperability between EU information systems in the field of borders and visa and amending Regulations (EC) No 767/2008, (EU) 2016/399, (EU) 2017/2226, (EU) 2018/1240, (EU) 2018/1726 and (EU) 2018/1861 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Decisions 2004/512/EC and 2008/633/JHA, as consolidated on 03/08/2021
- Travel documents (and the processing of biometrics therein)
 - Council Regulation (EC) No 2252/2004 of 13 December 2004 on standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States as consolidated on 26/09/2009
 - Commission Decision of 28/6/2006 laying down the technical specifications on the standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States
 - Commission Decision of 4/8/2011 amending Commission Decision C(2006) 2909 final laying down the technical specifications on the standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States
 - Commission implementing Decision of 30/9/2013 amending Commission Decision C(2006) 2909 final laying down the technical specifications on the standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States and Commission Decision C(2008) 8657 laying down a certificate policy as required in the technical specifications on the standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States and updating the normative reference documents
 - Council Regulation (EC) No 1030/2002 of 13 June 2002 laying down a uniform format for residence permits for third-country nationals, as consolidated on 21/11/2017

- Council Regulation (EC) No 1683/95 of 29 May 1995 laying down a uniform format for visas, as consolidated on 17/08/2017
- Regulation (EU) 2019/1157 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on strengthening the security of identity cards of Union citizens and of residence documents issued to Union citizens and their family members exercising their right of free movement
- Privacy and security of personal (and biometric) data
 - Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
 - Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA
 - Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC
- Cybersecurity of products and services
 - Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union
 - Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act)
- Artificial intelligence in the context of BCP technologies
 - Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain union legislative acts, COM/2021/206 final
- 2. The following stands also for the listing of Standards applicable to:
 - ePassports (and other e-MRTDs) and security-related aspects
 - Facial recognition algorithms/Iris recognition algorithms/Fingerprints recognition algorithms/etc
 - Multimodal biometrics enrolment and verification (and security related aspects)
 - Security of Border control points and communications
 - Security of storage media, mobile devices and contactless chips

- Mobile/Virtual ID
- Remote verification of ePassports using mobile devices
- Encryption

9. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the second updated version of the METICOS Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan along with a detailed reporting of the activities that took place during the period of interest. The document begins with an update of the METICOS Dissemination and Communication strategy (*chapter 2*) and provides a reporting of the dissemination activities in *chapter 3*. The deliverable continues with an extensive presentation of the H2020 BES Cluster along with the previous and upcoming activities (*chapter 4*). In *chapter 5*, the Monitoring and evaluation of the KPIs is presented. *Chapter 6* is a first draft of the exploitation plan for the centric output of the project, the METICOS platform, followed by *chapter 7* and the initial market analysis that will guide the consortium to create a feasible and sustainable final exploitation and commercialisation plan. Last, *chapter 8* contains the Regulatory and standardisation reporting, providing information about the European landscape.

METICOS's partnership aims to sustain project results beyond project duration, maximise its impact, exploit its outcomes, and achieve economic sustainability. This document explored the sustainability and exploitation potential of the METICOS project, with the aim to stipulate a strategic agreement based on the present document, to bind all project partners to implement a mutual strategy that will allow for durability. The report was created within the context of presenting an initial business model identified for the METICOS platform.

The final METICOS dissemination communication and exploitation plan (D11.3) will present a concrete view of the impact of the dissemination plan and the exploitation options, as these will be defined by the consortium, and will further define the needed actions for the commercialisation of the METICOS outcomes, including:

- the individual exploitation plans of each METICOS partner,
- the co-operative exploitation plans of the METICOS consortium, and
- a plan for follow-up commercial exploitation activities, to be pursued by interested partners.
- A completed market analysis for all METICOS exploitable results

10. Annexes

Annex I: METICOS dissemination and communication reporting

METICOS Dissemination & Communication reporting

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Disclaimer
The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

* Partner name

* Type of activity

- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
- Participation in a Workshop
- Participation in a Conference
- Participation in an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop (Networking events, Exhibitions, Symposia, Webinars etc.)
- Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects (Synergies)
- Training session
- Press release
- Newsletter
- Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)
- Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)
- Poster
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Video/film
- Other

* Title of event / activity / slogan

Location (venue / online)

* Date

Title of presentation (if applicable)

URL of the activity/recordings etc. (if applicable)

URL of the publication (if applicable)

Description to be added on the project website

Type of audience reached below. Please indicate ESTIMATED no. of persons reached per type of audience. Please select a type only if applicable (EC request).

	Industry	Research Community	Policymakers	Society (customers/Civil society organisations, general public)	Media	Other
No. of persons	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Please copy below any relevant links (e.g. to videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

Please upload any photos relevant material (e.g. videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

Figure 78 Print screen from the dissemination and communication reporting form from EU survey

Annex II: METICOS - Exploitation/innovation questionnaire for technical partners

METICOS - Exploitation/innovation questionnaire for technical partners

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Disclaimer ✕
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* Partner name

* Title of the METICOS exploitable output/innovation

* Briefly describe the METICOS output

* The exploitable output is

- under development
- already developed but not yet being exploited
- being exploited

* Characterise the type of output

- Significantly improved product
- New product
- Significantly improved service (except consulting ones)
- New service (except consulting ones)
- Significantly improved process
- New process
- Significantly improved marketing method
- New marketing method
- Significantly improved organisational method
- New organisational method
- Consulting services
- Other

* How do you intent to exploit the output/innivation?

- Introduce it to the market (commercial exploitation)
- Deploy it within a partner (internal exploitation: Changes in organisation, new internal processes implemented, etc.)
- For further research activities
- For standardisation activities
- By transferring the ownership of results
- Don't really know yet
- Other

* Briefly mention the exploitation activities you are planning to implement or you have already implemented (within the project's duration)

* Will you need assistance in identifying pathways for exploiting the output/innovation?

Yes

No

* Is there a clear owner of the exploitable output in the consortium or multiple owners?

A clear owner

Multiple owners

* Indicate which participant(s) is/are the key organisation(s) in the project delivering this output.

EUC

ICCS

NetU

NTNU

VUB

SIMAVI

AIT

JOAFG

MAGG

VILABS

Figure 79 Print screen from the Exploitation/innovation questionnaire form from EU survey